

ALL-Ready Project Deliverable 3.2 - Third Report of ALL-Ready pilot co-creation experiences

ALL-Ready – The European Agroecology Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: preparation phase

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Reports of ALL-Ready Pilot Co-Creation Experiences – Report n.3

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List of abbreviations

AE	Agroecology
LL	Living Lab
RI	Research Infrastructure
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
WP	Work Package
LCA	(Environmental) Life Cycle Assessment
SLCA	Social Life Cycle Analysis
EA	Economic Assessment
CA	Conservation Agriculture
AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
CSA	Coordination And Support Action
EC	European Commission
ACS	Agricultural Climate Solutions
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
GHG	Green House Gases
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
AMU	Antimicrobial Use
AMR	Antimicrobial Resistance
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
CBP	Capacity Building Programme

Abbreviations of Pilot Network Members

ISF	Institute for Sustainable Food
IF	Innovative Farmers
Lifewatch-ERIC	Lifewatch
Organic RDD	Organic Research Development and Demonstration Program
CROPSYS	CROPSYS
ÖMKi	ÖMKi On-Farm Living Lab
LLAEBIO	Living Lab on Agro-Ecology and Organic Agriculture in Flanders
ZAPVS	LTSER Zone Atelier Plaine & Val de Sèvre
Occitanum	Occitanie Agriculture Numérique
AAFC	Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada
PA4ALL	Precision Agriculture for All

ROADMAP	ROADMAP
REWET	Wetland observatories for rewetting of drained peatlands
CarbonFarm	CarbonFarm
OasYs	OasYs
CBIO	Centre for Circular Bioeconomy Production and Management of Agricultural Biomass
Guadalinfo	Guadalinfo Living Lab
Hessen	Hessen Practice Network
EMPHASIS	EMPHASIS
InoFA	Internet of Food Alliance
FiBL	FiBL On-farm LL
LIT Ouesterel	Laboratoire d'Innovation Territorial "Ouest Territoires d'Elevage"

Introduction

ALL-Ready is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Commission (EC) with the aim of preparing a framework for a future European network of Living Labs (LL) and Research Infrastructures (RI) that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. Based on the premise that agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, the project will contribute to addressing the multiple challenges that they are facing today, including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, and the degradation of soil and water quality.

The future European network of Living Labs (LL) and Research Infrastructures (RI) will promote transdisciplinary, highly participatory, inclusive, and coordinated experimentation in real life settings, ensure knowledge exchange at the EU level, and the delivery of series of long-term data on ecological processes applied to agriculture in diverse conditions across the EU. It will support farmers – at farm, landscape, and regional level - in understanding and implementing agroecological practices at the scale needed for significant positive economic, environmental and social impact.

This deliverable details the co-creation experiences of the ALL-Ready pilot network taking place in WP3. WP3 – besides coordinating stakeholder engagement activities - aims to build and run a small-scale pilot network in order to test the approaches, tools and recommendations developed across the project for the implementation of the future European network.

This document contains the following: first, the rationale, objectives, selection process, and general characteristics of the pilot network. It also gives a detailed presentation of all 20 pilot members using the framework for agroecology transition developed in WP1 (Chapter 1). Second, it shows the co-creation processes in which the pilot network participated and analyses the methods and experiences of the pilot network meetings (Chapter 2). Third, it also provides recommendations based on the co-creation experiences for the future European network on upscaling opportunities (Chapter 3).

This deliverable was a living document, updated each year of the project. This is last update of the deliverable.

1. The ALL-READY Pilot Network

1.1 Piloting the European Network of Agroecological LLs and RIs

The European Commission aims to launch a partnership (new co-funded instrument) entitled “Accelerating farming systems transition: agroecology living labs and research infrastructures” under the Horizon Europe research and innovation framework in 2023 ([AGROECOLOGY Partnership](#)). One of the aims of the partnership is to build and organise a European network of new and existing living labs and research infrastructures for knowledge sharing and co-creation on agroecology innovations at various scales across Europe. It will identify relevant existing LLs and RIs and animate the network to set the stage for a European-wide community accelerating agroecology transition. The network will develop tools for the sharing of best practices and a platform for knowledge exchange among the members, will promote the creation of new agroecology living labs and research infrastructure while ensuring cooperation within and outside the network (SCAR-AE 2021).

The ALL-Ready project contributed significantly to the creation of this future network through the development of its vision, mission, and framework for agroecology transition in Living Labs (LLs) and Research infrastructures (RIs) and through piloting a small-scale network of already existing LLs and RIs. This vision is “to accelerate the transition to agroecology throughout Europe by connecting and empowering place-based innovation from 2023 onwards through connecting agroecology LL/RIs and other open innovation initiatives across Europe that support practices for agriculture production that pilot, create and use diversity” (Mambrini-Doudet *at al.* 2022). The pilot network allowed real-life experimentation on the structuring and functioning of the future European network based on co-creative and participatory methods, and the lessons learnt can directly inform the setting up of the future network.

As the members in the ALL-Ready pilot network were agroecology living labs and research infrastructures, it is important to clarify the definitions used in this deliverable.

Living Labs (LLs) are open innovation ecosystems in real-life environments, which use iterative feedback processes throughout the lifecycle of an innovation. They operate as orchestrators among citizens, research organisations, companies, and government agencies. They focus on joint value co-creation, rapid prototyping, testing, and scaling-up innovations ([ENOLL](#)). The three basic operational principles supporting LL activities are i) co-creation, ii) user-centredness, iii) real life conditions. More specifically, agroecology living labs can be identified as initiatives that comply with the following set of criteria: i) co-creation of knowledge and innovation; ii) promotion of resilience, sustainability and diversity; iii) support for climate change adaptation and mitigation, iv) synergies between ecosystem functions; v) promotion of efficiency and responsibility in the use of natural resources; vi) development of circular and solidarity economies, value given to social and ecological justice. (Mambrini-Doudet *at al.* 2021).

Research Infrastructures (RIs) are open research facilities for experimentation at different scales (plot, farm, landscape level and networks). They are expected to contribute to bringing a corpus of knowledge for agroecology transition and are expected to have a central role in education, in providing data to stakeholders, and in providing services in an open science vision (Mambrini-Doudet *at al.* 2021).

A key assumption behind ALL-Ready was that RIs and LLs are instruments that have significant potential to contribute to amplifying the transition to agroecology in Europe.

1.1.1 Examples of existing networks

There are already networks in place, namely the Agriculture and Agri-food Working Group of the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) and the living lab network in the frame of the Agricultural Climate Solutions (ACS) programme financed by the Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada (AAFC), which serve as good examples for the pilot network and for the development of the future European Network of Agroecology LLs and RIs. However, these are also some substantial differences.

The Canadian Government-supported ACS was launched in 2018 as a nationwide network of agroecosystem living labs to foster the development and adoption of sustainable practices and technologies by Canadian farmers, to accelerate the response to climate change and other agri-environmental challenges – but without prominent support for research infrastructures.

On the other hand, ENoLL is an international non-profit association which aims to promote and enhance the Living Lab concept globally, by facilitating knowledge exchange, joint actions, and project partnerships among members. They operate several thematic working groups, one of which is the Agriculture and Agri-food Working Group consisting of agricultural living labs from around the world. The focus of the working group and ENoLL lacks the research infrastructure component, although some of the living labs in the network identify themselves as RIs as well. Moreover, many agricultural living labs within the ENoLL network do not operate in the agroecology domain, but rather study and contribute to conventional practices.

1.2 ALL-READY Pilot Network Objectives, Member Selection Process and Set-Up

1.2.1 Objectives

The pilot network had a triple objective:

- to act as a small-scale testbed to experiment, and to give feedback on the tools and recommendations developed in the ALL-Ready project (across WPs)
- to build strong links and cooperation between the different agroecology-focused living labs, research infrastructures and open innovation arrangements across Europe
- to co-create and realise joint network activities in line with the common agroecology interests of the pilot members.

1.2.2 Member selection

Between May and June 2021, a selection survey was launched to identify forerunner agroecology LL/RIs from the 13 partner countries. The survey was structured to gather general information and defining characteristics of the applicants in relation to specific agroecology LL/RI elements. In addition, the survey mapped individual needs and expectations from the pilot network.

The selection process took place between July-September 2021 following general network-level and individual selection criteria. The general criteria were designed to obtain an even distribution of geographic representation, scale of users, maturity level, scope of activities and agroecology scale for the whole pilot network. The individual criteria have been distinguished on LL and RI level, assuring that initiatives comply with the features of an agroecology LL or RI. Selected LLs had to fulfil five of the following criteria:

- fully describe their agroecological practices and research using LL methodology,
- showcase activities or research covering transdisciplinary, mainly socio-economic aspects of agroecology,

- describing their users, the different types of stakeholders and how they are involved in their co-creative processes,
- describing the real-life context,
- describing their products, services developed,
- defining the impacts of the initiative and their contribution to the agroecology transition.

Selected RIs also had to fulfil five of the following criteria:

- fully describe their agroecological practices and research,
- defining the impacts of the initiative and their contribution to the agroecology transition,
- describing the research resources that are provided by the initiative,
- describing the tools/practices that are used by the initiative,
- describing their users, the different types of stakeholders and how they are involved in their co-creative processes.

After the evaluation done by the consortium members, 15 initiatives were selected for the pilot network. In addition to the 15 pilot network members (ISF, IF, Lifewatch-ERIC, Organic RDD, CROPSYS, ÖMKi, LLAEBIO, ZAPVS, Occitanum, PA4ALL, ROADMAP, REWET, CarbonFarm, OasYs, Biobase), two external advisor organisations (AAFC and Guadalinfo) have been added, to support the network. Preparations for the network set-up were organised between October and November 2021, while the first pilot meeting took place online in December 2021 and the 2nd pilot meeting between 4-5th July in Ghent, Belgium. In order to remain open and inclusive, a new selection period was conducted between July and October 2022 based on the results of the „Accelerating the agroecology transition: Your potential role and benefits of contributing to a European network of living labs and research infrastructures“ questionnaire developed by WP1. Applicants were screened and interviewed following a set of inclusion criteria for agroecology living labs and research infrastructures (D1.2). An additional 5 initiatives (Hessen, LIT Ouesterel, InoFA, FiBL on-farm LL and EMPHASIS) were selected, resulting in a total of 20 members in the pilot network. The new members were introduced at the 3rd pilot network meeting organised between 21-23 November 2022, in Budapest, Hungary. The members are very different in size and objectives. Some of them are certified living labs by ENoLL, but the majority are open innovation structures in the form of national, territorial networks, LL-like projects, or experimental sites.

In **Appendix 1**, all 20 pilot members are presented in detail based on the four key features of agroecology living labs and research infrastructures (context, aim, activities, participants) in the framework for agroecology transition elaborated by WP1. Each member presentation also contains additional features on the achievements and methods used in the initiatives.

1.3 Characteristics and Activities of the Pilot Network

1.3.1 Characteristics

The pilot network consisted of 20 initiatives of which twelve identify as AE LL, and eight as AE RI. From the advisors, Guadalinfo is a living lab while ACS identifies as both a LL and RI:

Living Labs:

Belgium - LLAEBIO (Living Lab on Agro-Ecology and Organic Agriculture in Flanders)
 Hungary – ÖMKi On-Farm Living Lab
 Serbia – PA4ALL (Precision Agriculture for All)
 Denmark –, ROADMAP, CarbonFarm
 France – Occitanum, LIT Ouesterel
 UK - Innovative Farmers
 Germany – Hessen Practice Network
 Switzerland – FiBL On-farm LL
 Greece - InoFA

Research Infrastructures:

Spain – LifeWatch-ERIC

Denmark – ReWet DK, CROPSYS, Biobase, Organic RDDP

France – OasYs, LTSER Zone Atelier Plaine & Val de Sèvre

UK - Institute of Sustainable Food

Germany - EMPHASIS

Advisors:

Canada – Agricultural Climate Solutions (LL&RI)

Spain – Guadalinfo (LL)

1.3.1.1 Geographic representation

The composition of the network was very diverse, representing all four European regions (Figure 1):

- **Northern** (CROPSYS, REWET, Biobase, Organic RDDP, CarbonFarm, ROADMAP)
- **Southern** (LifeWatch-ERIC, Occitanum, InoFA)
- **Western** (ISF, LLAEBIO, OASYS, ZAPVS, Innovative Farmers, LIT Ouesterel, Hessen, EMPHASIS, FiBL)
- **Eastern Europe** (PA4ALL, ÖMKi)

Figure 1. European map of the pilot network members

1.3.1.2 Scope of activities

The members also differed in terms of the geographic scope of their activities:

- local (ZAPVS, Occitanum)
- regional (REWET, LLAEBIO, Hessen, Lit Ouesterel)
- national (PA4ALL, ÖMKi, CROPSYS, OASYS, Biobase, IF, Organic RDD, CarbonFarm, InoFA)
- international (ISF, LifeWatch-ERIC, ROADMAP, EMPHASIS, FiBL)

1.3.1.3 Maturity level of the initiatives

The initiatives also represented diverse maturity levels, from very young to more experienced:

- short lifespan (<1 year) (Occitanum)
- medium lifespan (1-2 years) (LLAEBIO, Hessen, Lit Ouesterel, InoFA)
- long (mature) lifespan (2-4 years) (PA4ALL, ISF, LifeWatch-ERIC, ROADMAP, Organic RDD, EMPHASIS)
- very long (very mature) lifespan (>4 years) (ÖMKi, CROPSYS, OasYs, REWET, Biobase, ZAPVS, IF, CarbonFarm, FiBL)

1.3.1.4 Scale of users in the initiatives

Network member initiatives also differed regarding the scale of users (for AE LLs, users are usually the farmers, but often stakeholders in the agri-food value chain; for AE RIs, they are researchers, as well as, occasionally, farmers, advisors, and citizens) from small to large-scale initiatives:

- small scale (< 50 users) (PA4ALL, CROPSYS, LifeWatch-ERIC, OasYs, CarbonFarm, Hessen, EMPHASIS)
- medium scale (50 – 200 users) (LLAEBIO, ÖMKi, ROADMAP, Occitanum, Biobase, Organic RDD, Lit Ouesterel, InoFA, FiBL)
- large scale (> 200 users) (ISF, REWET, ZAPVS, IF)

1.3.2 Activities

The activities of the pilot network were interlinked with basically all WPs of the project and were formed to achieve the three main objectives, (1) aiming to build a community through collaborative activities, (2) providing feedback on the concepts and recommendations developed by ALL-Ready and (3) co-creating different tools and programmes through designing, prototyping, testing, and evaluating during the project lifetime.

The co-creation activities in the pilot network included the co-development of the structure, operations, and joint network activities in WP3, the co-design of a capacity building programme within WP5 and the building of a Virtual Lab tool in WP6. These activities consisted of multiple stages and are running in parallel until the end of the project. Moreover, their participation was crucial in the yearly pilot network meetings.

In addition, the pilot network was also consulted, and it gives feedback occasionally on concepts and documents developed by other WPs: the framework, criteria, vision and mission and questionnaire for agroecology transition in WP1, identification of best LL/RI initiatives across Europe in WP2, co-construction of the sustainability of the future European network in WP4 or sharing of news and updates about themselves.

2. Co-creation process in the Pilot Network

2.1 Co-creation of value: scientific background

Although co-creation has now become an extremely widespread and popularised term, even a review of relevant literature does not provide a clear definition. This term is used in corporate marketing, business, and consumer-centered discourse just as frequently as in public-private partnerships, multi-stakeholder platforms, and living labs involving citizens who focus on innovation and research. Co-creation in the corporate sector describes the process of value creation through the active collaboration of the consumers, who are allowed to co-develop the product and service experience to fit their needs and context (Kambil *et al.* 1999.) This is a continuous cooperation that takes place between the firm and the consumers, supported by the consumers (Jansen and Pieters, 2017).

However, for the purpose of this deliverable, in the ALL-Ready project, the understanding developed by living labs on co-creation is more fitting. Co-creation in living labs is a living concept and refers to a form of open innovation, where the development of new value happens in cooperation between the experts and a variety of stakeholders from industry, research, public institutions, and civil society, in which the inputs of the user play a central role (Schumacher and Feurstein 2007, Hagy *et al.* 2016, Mambrini-Doudet *et al.* 2021). Also, the involvement of multiple stakeholders creates a multi-contextual scene in which the actors engage and interact with other stakeholders during every step of the co-creation process from problem definition to piloting (Ballon *et al.* 2005, Kreiling and Paunov 2021).

In the context of ALL-Ready, the focus is on agroecology living labs and research infrastructures. Mambrini-Doudet *et al.* (2021) highlights that the co-creation in agroecology living labs support the transition to agroecology, and the co-development of knowledge through the sharing of tacit and implicit knowledge. Also, including the knowledge of local communities is particularly important, as is fostering the participation of all relevant stakeholders in agroecology at local and global scales (farmers to consumer associations). This can mobilise and bring together complementary and transversal agroecology expertise which increases the speed and uptake of innovations while also increasing awareness and relevance of agroecology transition and, at the same time, addressing socio-economic challenges via the involvement of civil society. Research infrastructures are more focused on providing services and facilities mainly for the research community, but sometimes for other societal actors as well. Although co-creation is not a requirement, there are agroecology RIs that support agroecology transition through the co-design and co-development of specific Virtual Research Environments applied to agroecology research. Moreover, during systemic experiments, including the redesign of systems or long-term monitoring, other stakeholders such as farmers and advisors are becoming more and more involved, therefore creating space for similar open innovation and co-creation processes happening in living labs. (e.g., networks of farms at regional or national level, platforms where collective innovation is ongoing, and where scientists are engaged) (Mambrini-Doudet *et al.* 2021)

According to Puerari *et al.* (2018), five common elements of co-creation in living labs can be distinguished, which not only exist in themselves but often influence and relate to one another:

- 1) Purpose of co-creation: There are two possible purposes of co-creation. Either working towards a common goal or an outcome, or focusing on learning itself, with the stakeholders cooperating on knowledge creation or sharing, or to learn from one another, and to develop networks or a community. The two can run simultaneously as well.

2) Formal and informal co-creation:

a) formal: environment organised by initiators or intermediaries which is constructed around defined procedures and steps, and the participants are often selected based on criteria that makes them valuable for the co-creation process.

b) informal: the co-creation process emerges organically out of necessity or out of shared goals. The environment is not organised by official planning or procedures, and both the selection of participants and the rules develop over time.

3) Ownership: Running the co-creation process requires the definition of different roles and the provision of the right tools to the right people. Depending on who determines the roles, the intermediary or initiator often takes the dominant role and defines the direction of the co-creation process. But the intermediary can open up the process to all stakeholders to share ownership.

4) Motivation for co-creation: Since co-creation, like any other activity, can create a variety of costs for the stakeholders (time-consuming, monetary costs, etc.), the benefits of participation need to be clearly articulated. The motivation of the stakeholders is influenced by their goals, resources, and expectations. The motivation can be intrinsic (without any external influence, for the sake of co-creation) or extrinsic (monetary compensation, future investment, recognition, etc.)

5) Places of co-creation: Co-creation occurs in a place-based (often local) socio-spatial context which also helps when analysing the specific conditions in which co-creation takes place. This contributes to the wider adaptation and implementation of an innovation within a given local community.

However, each element has its own challenges that needs to be tackled during every co-creation process (Table 1).

Element	Definition	Challenge	Solution
Purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Either working towards a common goal or an outcome The goal can be the learning itself, knowledge creation or sharing 	How to engage all stakeholders?	Shared goals, develop close personal relations, build trust
Formal or informal co-creation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Formal: environment organised by intermediaries, with defined procedures, participants are selected Informal: the co-creation process emerges out of necessity, no official planning, no selection of participants 	How to create effective governance, operations, and structure?	Plan of actions, procedures, working groups, modes of operation
Ownership	Stakeholders have control over the steps and decision-making of the co-creation process.	How to develop a sense of ownership and use commonly created data and knowledge?	Detailed guidance, formalisation of contracts
Motivation	Reasons of stakeholders for participating in the co-creation process.	How to incentivise processes and participants in the long run?	Reward system, recognition, benefit package, monitoring of participation

Spaces and places	Co-creation is bound to the place and local context in which it occurs.	How to adapt to changing environments (community, institutional, etc.)?	Flexibility, inclusive management
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Table 1. Corresponding challenges and solutions of the five co-creation elements

Lastly, the co-creation experience of individual actors also helps to evaluate the overall co-creation process. This experience is defined as a personal knowledge or value creation process, which is ongoing and dependant on the degree and nature of the individual’s involvement with other stakeholders (Prahalad and Ramaswamy 2004, Randall 2011). This personal experience also encompasses the individual’s subjective feelings, state of mind, competency, expertise, and enjoyment resulting from the co-creation activity (Füller *et al.* 2011).

The ALL-Ready pilot members’ personal experiences about the co-creation processes taking place in the pilot network is evaluated in Section 2.2.6.

2.2 Co-creation in the Pilot Network

2.2.1 Different co-creation processes in the pilot network

During the ALL-Ready project, the pilot network acted as a testbed to not only experiment and give feedback on the different concepts and recommendations developed, but to co-create and co-design new tools and activities for the pilot members and the larger agroecology community as well.

This co-creation process started in the first pilot network meeting, using different methods or a mixture of methods, and is being applied through three work packages: (1) WP3 - where the members co-created joint network activities, and operations, (2) WP5 – where the members co-designed and implemented a capacity building programme and (3) WP6 – where the pilot members also co-designed the Virtual Lab tool.

Besides co-creation, the members are also heavily involved through consulting and informing on specific topics or concepts in WP1, WP2, WP4 and WP7, but this involvement is not detailed in this document as it does not constitute a multistage co-creative process done only with the pilot members.

a. Joint Pilot Network Activities

Figure 2. Co-creation process of the joint pilot network activities in WP3

The co-creation of joint network activities and operations was a process consisting of five main steps (Figure 2) starting from the first pilot network meeting until the end of the project

in 2023. However, the resulting experiences and lessons learnt are expected to contribute to the future network. The 1st step in this process was the collection of expectations and needs of the pilot network from the members in the form of an online selection survey in June 2021. The results of the survey were validated and finally decided on during the first pilot network meeting in December 2021, where the members also mapped their collaboration potential and joint network activities as a 2nd step through workshops. The 3rd step in the process was the finalisation of the collaborative themes resulting from the mapping exercise and a co-design of an action plan and supporting operations and structure in June 2022. There was approx. 1,5 years to complete the tasks laid down in the network’s action plan (by October 2023) which was the 4th step. In parallel, the network also evaluated their co-creation experiences between March – July 2023 as 5th step at the end of the project.

b. Developing an implementation plan for the European Network

Figure 3. Co-creation process of the implementation plan in WP4

The involvement of the pilot network members for developing the implementation plan for the future European Network follows an adapted participatory process that is modified to the short time frame available. The development of the implementation plan involves the pilot network members in three main steps of a) understanding and exploring, b) synthesising and identifying ideas, and c) prioritising and co-designing recommendations (Figure 3), which are carried out in parallel with, and build on, the co-creation activities in WP3 and in WP5, from the third pilot network meeting until the end of the project in 2023. The first step was to understand the purpose of the future European Network and to explore views on key factors of its sustainability, done in a workshop at the third pilot network meeting in November 2022, which fed into the structure and outline of the implementation plan. In the second step key factors of the sustainability of the future European Network synthesised and pilot network members identified key elements of the implementation plan in an online workshop in March 2023. The participative process concluded by a final third step, in which pilot network members prioritised key elements of the implementation plan and derived recommendations for ensuring the long-term sustainability of the European Network at the fourth pilot network meeting in June 2023. WP4 process and its results are detailed in D4.2.

c. Developing the capacity building programme

Figure 4. Co-creation process of the capacity building programme in WP5

The development of the capacity building programme for the future network in the frame of WP5 was also a co-creative process consisting of four main stages (Figure 4) running in parallel with the co-creation of joint network activities in WP3 from the first pilot network meeting until the end of the project in 2023. The 1st stage was the scoping exercise to identify necessary competencies and skills to run an AE LL/RI and to transition to agroecology, done in a workshop in the first pilot network meeting in December 2021, which fed into the design of the programme. The capacity building programme was prototyped in the 2nd stage by the members through co-design workshops between July-December 2022. Finally, the programme was tested and evaluated through three trainings and a workshop with member LL/RIs between March-September 2023.

d. Co-designing the Virtual Lab

The co-design of the Virtual Lab - an online tool to make it easier for members to find and securely access agroecology LL/RI related data and use it in innovative ways – was also a simultaneously running process consisting of six steps (Figure 5) with the two previously mentioned co-creation courses. The 1st step was the identification of pilot member needs in relation to the Virtual Lab through a workshop during the first pilot network meeting in December 2021. The 2nd step was the co-creation of value and features for the Lab with the members in early 2022. Then the Virtual was prototyped and tested by the members as a 3rd step and evaluated in the 4th step in November 2022 through a series of workshops. As a 5th step, the initial prototype was further improved based on the evaluation and finalised in early 2023. Finally, the tool was implemented via two training workshops with the members in June 2023.

Figure 5. Co-creation process of the Virtual Lab tool in WP6

2.2.2 Most Significant Events: Pilot Network Meetings

The Most Significant Events were key events that took place since the start of the pilot network until the end of the ALL-Ready project. These events provided the basis for analysing the experiences in the pilot network. Four major events occurred in the form of pilot network meetings and three smaller ones: a 1,5 hour long catch-up call with the members in April 2022, the selection of 5 new members into the network in November 2022 and a 2-hour online progress meeting in March 2023. However, the smaller events will not be discussed in detail in the analysis of the pilot network experiences.

The 1st, 2nd, 3rd, and 4th meetings were a combination of presentations and active workshop sessions, each organised and facilitated by WPs 1-3-4-5 and 6.

Table 2 summarises all the events (date, place, organisers, and objectives) that have occurred in the pilot network:

Most Significant Event	Date and Place	Objective
1 st pilot network meeting	13-14th December 2021, online, organised by ÖMKi	<p>The overall objective of the meeting was to launch the ALL-Ready pilot network which has been in preparation since July 2021. To reach this aim, specific objectives were also pursued:</p> <p>(1) to familiarise members with the project through introductory presentations about ALL-Ready, the aims of the pilot network and the European Partnership “Accelerating farming systems transition: agroecology living labs and research infrastructures”,</p> <p>(2) to allow the members to get to know each other and initiate cooperation through the pilot member presentations and the match-making workshop,</p> <p>(3) to present and ask feedback from the members on already developed concepts of the project such as the inclusion criteria, vision and mission for the future network or the use of the online selection tool and</p> <p>(4) to contribute to the ongoing work of different WPs with members’ expertise through the five workshops.</p>
2 nd pilot Network Meeting	4-5 July 2022, in Ghent Belgium, hybrid, organised by ÖMKi and ILVO	<p>The overall objective of the meeting was to build on the outcomes of the 1st pilot meeting and continue the work started in WPs 3-4-5-6:</p> <p>(1) to operationalise the collaborative themes of the pilot network by agreeing what activities/tasks are feasible to do by the end of the project</p> <p>(2) to share inspiring examples of co-creation methods and involving stakeholders and to help members to find solutions to their related challenges through peer-to peer support and advice,</p> <p>(3) to present the main 'needs for capacity building' identified during the first phase (scoping of the capacity building plan) and to co-decide with the members on the prototype (content and format) for capacity building material</p> <p>(4) to validate the initial set of functionalities for the Virtual Lab identified by the members on the 1st pilot meeting and to refine and</p>

		understand the reasons behind these functionalities.
3 rd pilot Network Meeting	21-23 November 2022, in Budapest, Hungary, hybrid, organised by ÖMKi	<p>The overall aim of the meeting was to build on the outcomes of the 1st and 2nd pilot meetings and continue the work started in WPs 3-4-5-6:</p> <p>(1) to give an update on the progress with the action plan tasks for all members and to propose and agree on new tasks for the network</p> <p>(2) to learn about the use of three practical tools for co-creation to address the gap between scientists and farmers that the members can use in their own LL/RIs</p> <p>(3) to reflect on the main purpose of the future European Network and to explore key issues for its governance that would help ensuring its long-term sustainability,</p> <p>(4) to discuss and identify gaps in the first prototype of the capacity building programme and the gathered capacity building materials</p> <p>(5) to train participants on the pre-operational version of the Agroecology Virtual Lab and validate the current version of the platform.</p>
4 th pilot Network Meeting	14-16 June, Montpellier, France - hybrid, organised by ÖMKi and INRAE Montpellier	<p>The overall objective of the meeting was to build on the outcomes of the 2nd and 3rd pilot meetings and contribute to finalising the work in WPs 3-4-5-6:</p> <p>(1) to give an update on the progress with the action plan tasks for all members and to come up with recommendations for the future network based on pilot co-creation experiences,</p> <p>(2) to train the members on systems thinking and how it supports them in their daily work and to train the on the use of tools and methods relevant in each phase of innovation management and share some facilitation techniques, a powerful tool for capturing user insights and needs in agroecology projects,</p> <p>(3) to introduce the concept, approach and structure of the implementation plan for the future European Network and to reflect on key issues of selected dimensions that the guidance document needs to cover,</p> <p>(4) to present and validate the last release of the Agroecology Virtual Lab and the onboarding process of new users and to</p>

		discuss the principles of innovation management focused on data sharing and use and intellectual property rights.
Catch-up call	22 April 2022, online, organised by ÖMKi	The main aim was to provide an update about the developments of the pilot network, since December 2021, discuss the results of the 1 st meeting and news from members, and settle a date for the 2 nd meeting.
Selection of new members	July – October 2022, questionnaire, online interviews	To keep the network open and inclusive with members meeting the inclusion criteria developed in WP1.
Online Progress Meeting	17 March 2023, online, organised by ÖMKi	The objectives were to co-design the pilot co-creation evaluation process with the members and give an update on the progress made with the action plan.

Table 2. Most Significant Events (date, place, organisers, and objectives) that have occurred in the pilot network

The meeting agendas and the list of participants are detailed in **Appendices 2 and 3**.

2.2.3 Co-creation methods applied during the Pilot Network Meetings

Six different methods were applied during the three pilot network meetings, each designed to differently engage the members to reach the desired goals which are summarised in Table 3.

The following methods were used:

1. Validation session: this method invited participants to work on and discuss a predefined set of topics and ideas to spark debate and arrive at a common understanding or set of preferences. This method was applied during the WP3 workshops in the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, and 4th pilot network meetings and during WP5-6 workshops in the 2nd, 3rd and 4th pilot network meetings.
2. Mapping: this method involved collecting information verbally or in written form from participants on a given area of interest, and then recording it on an online workboard or some type of 'map' that the group can logically and visually follow and constantly give feedback. This was the primary method that was used by WP3-5-6 workshops in the 1st pilot network meeting.
3. Matchmaking: this method helped to identify and connect (match) members, initiatives (LL/RIs) with common agroecology interests, activities, expertise, experiences and/or strengths, which has created collaborative connections, themes, linkages and realising opportunities that mutually benefit both parties. This method was applied only during the WP3 workshop in the 1st pilot network meeting.
4. Prioritisation: this method supports the members to prioritise a list of tasks or actions in very different manners in order to increase efficiency and clarity among tasks, deadlines and responsibilities. This method was used during the WP3 and WP5 workshops in the 2nd pilot network meeting.
5. Peer Assist: this method brings together all pilot members in a structured facilitated session where 1-2 peer members were invited to provide their experience, insights and knowledge to the rest of the network on a problem, challenge, but also to draw lessons from all members' knowledge and experience. This method was applied during the WP3 Learning roundtable workshop in the 2nd pilot meeting.

6. Carousel Brainstorming: this method provides space for small groups for new information to be learned or existing information to be reviewed through movement, conversation, and reflection. This method was used during the WP3 Learning roundtable workshop in the 3rd pilot network meeting.

Table 3. The goals and methods used during the WP3-5-6 related workshops of the four network meetings.

	Goals	Method(s)
WP3 co-creation workshops		
Joint activities for the pilot network (1st pilot network meeting)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to validate the inputs given by the members during the pilot member selection process (May-June 2021) about their individual expectations and needs from the pilot network and individual agroecology interests, to allow members to get to know each other's LL/RIs activities better while mapping the cooperation potential between them based on their agroecology interests and activities to lay the groundwork for future collaboration, to co-create joint activities for the pilot network. 	Online workshop: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> two validation sessions mapping in two groups match-making in two groups
Operationalising the collaborative themes (2nd pilot network meeting)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to operationalise the collaborative themes of the pilot network resulting from the 1st meeting by agreeing what activities/tasks are feasible to do by the end of the project, to arrive to a priority list of tasks. 	Hybrid workshop <ul style="list-style-type: none"> validation session prioritisation
Learning roundtable: Best practices for co-creation and involving stakeholders (2nd pilot network meeting)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to share inspiring examples of co-creation methods and involving stakeholders, to help members to find solutions to their related issues and challenges through peer-to-peer support and advice. 	Hybrid workshop: Peer Assist in two groups
Pilot network activity update (3rd and 4th pilot network meetings)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to give an update on the progress with the action plan tasks for all members, to propose and agree on new tasks for the network. 	Hybrid workshop: validation session
Learning Roundtable: Co-creation tools to address the gap between the needs of scientists and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to inform the members about three practical tools for co-creation and stakeholder engagement to address the gap between scientists and farmers 	Hybrid workshop: Carousel Brainstorm in three groups

farmers (3rd pilot network meeting)	<p>that they can use in their own LL/RIs,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> to learn about the implementation and use of these tools through situational exercises. 	
Joint reflection on pilot co-creation activities (4th pilot network meeting)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to share the results of the pilot network evaluation questionnaire conducted in April 2023, and discuss in depth emerging topics and issues of the questionnaire, to come up with recommendations for the future Network based on the experiences of the pilot network. 	Hybrid workshop: validation session in two groups
WP5 co-creation workshops		
Exploring the added value of a future network and competencies for transition to agroecology and to run LL/RI (1st pilot network meeting)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to collect inputs from the members on the needed competencies to (1) foster transition to agroecology in general and (2) set up and run an agroecology living lab and/or research infrastructure. 	Online workshop: mapping in two groups
What competencies and skills can a European Network improve? Prototyping the capacity building programme (2nd pilot network meeting)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to present and validate the main 'needs for capacity building' identified during the first phase (scoping of the capacity building plan), to co-decide with the pilot network on a prototype for capacity building material (prioritisation) and forms (training, guidelines, webinar, database, etc.). 	Hybrid workshop: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> validation session prioritisation
Co-designing the capacity building Training items (3rd pilot network meeting)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to present and discuss the first prototype of the capacity building programme and the gathered capacity building materials, to identify the gaps in the first prototype of the capacity building programme. 	In-person workshop: validation session
Capacity building training (4th pilot network meeting)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to train the members on systems thinking, on living lab model, real-life experimentation and facilitation techniques as part of the broader capacity building programme. 	In-person training with group exercise
WP6 co-creation workshops		

Building a Virtual Lab (1st pilot network meeting)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to provide an introduction about a Virtual Lab and what it is used for, • to launch the co-design of the Virtual Lab for Agroecology by the identification of the needs from the pilot network. 	Online workshop session: mapping in two groups
How can a virtual environment support a European Network? Functionalities of the Virtual Lab (2nd pilot network meeting)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to validate the initial set of functionalities identified with the members of the pilot network during the 1st meeting, • to launch a discussion to refine them and understand the reasons behind these functionalities. 	Hybrid workshop: validation session
Discussing the Agroecology Virtual Lab - testing version (3rd pilot network meeting)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to train participants on the pre-operational version of the Agroecology Virtual Lab (AE Virtual Lab) and validate the current version of the platform. 	Hybrid workshop: validation session
Finalising the Agroecology Virtual Lab and discussing innovation, data and IPR management (4th pilot network meeting)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to validate the last release of the Agroecology Virtual Lab and the onboarding process of new users, • to discuss principles for innovation management focused on data sharing and use and intellectual property rights. 	In-person workshop: validation session

2.2.4 Co-creation experiences of the Pilot Network Meetings

In the final version of this deliverable, the co-creation experiences of the four pilot network meetings were assessed step by step on the elements of co-creation, types of members involved, format, results, feedback on the experiences, and challenges.

2.2.4.1 Co-creation workshop elements of the four pilot network meetings

Tables 4-6 detail the analysis of the WP3-5-6 co-creation workshops of the four pilot network meetings based on the five elements of co-creation.

Table 4. Assessment of WP3 co-creation workshops based on the five elements of co-creation

	Step 1: Co-creation of joint collaborative activities for the pilot network	Step 2: Operationalizing the collaborative themes + Learning roundtable	Step 3: Pilot network activity update + Learning roundtable	Step 4: Pilot network activity update + Joint reflection on pilot co-creation activities
Purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working towards the realisation of joint network activities as an outcome. Building a network and community of AE LLs and RIs for sharing and creating knowledge and best practices. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Refining and operationalising the collaborative themes resulting from the 1st pilot network meeting (joint network activities) by creating an action plan for the network. Learn and share inspiring examples of co-creation methods used by members. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Checking on the progress with the action plan tasks for all members. Updating the action plan with new tasks. learn and train members about the usage of three specific co-creation tools through situational exercises. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Finalising the action plan tasks with the members. Sharing and discussing the results of the pilot network evaluation questionnaire. Drawing up recommendations for the future network on upscaling opportunities.
Formal/Informal	Formal: a targeted, organised environment by ALL-Ready, defined procedures, members went through selection	Formal	Formal	Formal
Ownership	After the first step of workshops, it is difficult to judge the ownership. Currently, the coordinator of the pilot network has the biggest ownership over the co-creation processes, the steps are pre-planned, but the decision-making over these steps will be opened up to the	Through the preparation of Step 2 and the action plan development, the members started to gain ownership of the co-creation process. The decision-making over the actions/tasks of the plan was open to all members. The Learning Roundtable was conceptualised and	Through the preparation of Step 3 and the action plan update, the members had ownership of the co-creation process. The decision-making over the actions/tasks of the plan was open to all members. The Learning Roundtable was	Through the preparation of Step 4, the members had ownership of the co-creation process. The decision-making on the actions/tasks of the plan was open to all members. The evaluation process

	members just as the structuring of the network.	facilitated by the members themselves.	conceptualised and facilitated by the members themselves.	was fully co-designed by the members.
Motivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Networking and knowledge exchange: to get to know other scientists and farmers from other LL/RIs, share experiences what other initiatives are doing – co-creation and meaningful research, knowledge exchange with other countries - explore the results they obtain (generic or not), and see whether they obtain the same results or not in a different site. Discovering new agroecological practices, inspire other scientists to work on agroecological systems. Teaming up with others based on similar goals, screening for potential collaboration. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Having a clear, structured action plan for the pilot network that serves as a reference point for all members for what the network wants to achieve and how by the end of the project. Cooperating in tasks that members are interested in and can learn from one another. In-person networking and experience/insight sharing on different co-creation methods. Finding solutions to LL/RI co-creation challenges through peer support. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Having a clear, structured action plan for the pilot network that serves as a reference point for all members for what the network wants to achieve and how by the end of the project. Cooperating in tasks that members are interested in and can learn from one another. Cooperative learning used both to discover and discuss background knowledge (co-creation) prior to studying a new tool, and to evoke informal discussions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Complete the action plan and look back what was achieved over the two years together that can be taken up by the future network. Reflect and draw lessons from the co-creation experiences and activities of the pilot network that can be used to improve member LL/RI activities. Transition into the future European Network.

Spaces/places	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online sphere, each member joining from home environments representing their own local LL/RI networks. • Wider space is the environment of the pilot network itself. 	Structured, facilitated hybrid environment within the pilot network (majority of members attending in-person, a few online).	Structured, facilitated hybrid environment within the pilot network (majority of members attending in-person, a few online).	Structured, facilitated hybrid environment within the pilot network (majority of members attending in-person, a few online).
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Table 5. Assessment of the WP5 co-creation workshops based on the five elements of co-creation

	Step 1: Capacity building programme: Exploring the competencies and skills for transition to agroecology and to run LL/RI	Step 2: What competencies and skills can a European Network improve? Prototyping the capacity building programme	Step 3: Co-designing the capacity building training items	Step 4: Capacity building trainings
Purpose	Preparing a capacity building programme to support the transition to agroecology by promoting agroecology, LL, and RI approaches.	Validating the main 'needs for capacity building' identified during Step 1 and arriving to a prototype capacity building material with different forms (training, guidelines, webinar, database, etc.).	Validating first prototype of the capacity building programme and the gathered capacity building materials after Step 2 and identifying possible gaps.	Training the members on systems thinking, on living lab model, real-life experimentation, and facilitation techniques as part of the broader capacity building programme.
Formal/Informal	Formal	Formal	Formal	Formal
Ownership	Currently, the coordinator of the pilot network and WP5 partners have the biggest ownership over the co-creation process, the steps are pre-planned, but the decision-making over these steps will be opened up to the members.	Currently, the WP5 partners have the biggest ownership over the co-creation process, the steps are pre-planned, but the decision-making over these steps are opened up to the members.	Currently, the WP5 partners have the biggest ownership over the co-creation process, the steps are pre-planned, but the decision-making over these steps are opened up to the members.	WP5 partners and external trainers had the biggest ownership of the process. Steps were decided together with the members, but they were merely participants at the trainings.

Motivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improving and developing further member LL/RI practices and the skills of LL/RI stakeholders. Tailored trainings, tools, and guides for the members on how to build, run and scale-up an AE LL/RIs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribution to a prototype capacity building programme from which members will directly benefit from through tailored trainings, tools, and guides on how to build, run and scale-up an AE LL/RIs. Improving and developing further member LL/RI practices, co-creation methods and knowledge on agroecology. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribution to a prototype capacity building programme from which members will directly benefit from through tailored trainings, tools, and guides on how to build, run and scale-up an AE LL/RIs. Improving and developing further member LL/RI practices, co-creation methods and knowledge on agroecology. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learning and exchanging about topics and related skills and competences that members are lacking or less familiar with: systems thinking, real-life experimentation and facilitation techniques. Using the learnt skills in the everyday life of members' LL/RIs, in order to improve.
Spaces/places	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Online Wider space is the environment of the pilot network itself 	Structured, facilitated hybrid environment within the pilot network (majority of members attending in-person, a few online)	Structured, facilitated in-person environment within the pilot network	Structured, facilitated in-person environment with the members.

Table 6. Assessment of the WP6 co-creation workshops based on the five elements of co-creation

	Step 1: Building the Virtual Lab	Step 2: How can a virtual environment support a European Network? Functionalities of the Virtual Lab	Step 3: Discussing the Agroecology Virtual Lab - testing version	Step 4: Finalising the Agroecology Virtual Lab and discussing innovation, data and IPR management
Purpose	Co-designing and testing the Agroecology Virtual Lab tool to find, share, store, use, access, visualise and analyse agroecology LL/RI related data.	Validating the initial set of functionalities identified in Step 1 with the members.	Training members on the first prototype of the Agroecology Virtual Lab and validating the current version of the platform.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Finalising the Agroecology Virtual Lab. Discussing principles for innovation

	to improve the knowledge about agroecology practices.			management focused on data sharing and use and intellectual property rights.
Formal/Informal	Formal	Formal	Formal	Formal
Ownership	Currently, the coordinator of the pilot network and WP6 have the biggest ownership over the co-creation process, the steps are pre-planned, but the decision-making over these steps will be opened up to the members.	Currently, WP6 partners have the biggest ownership over the co-creation process, the steps are pre-planned, but the decision-making over these steps are opened up to the members.	Currently, WP6 partners have the biggest ownership over the co-creation process, the steps are pre-planned, but the decision-making over these steps are opened up to the members.	WP6 partners have the biggest ownership of the co-creation process, the steps are pre-planned, but the decision-making on these steps are opened up to the members.
Motivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connecting with other RI/LLs through data-sharing. Improving member understanding of agroecological processes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribution to the development of the Virtual Lab from which members will directly benefit from through using the platform for connecting with peer experts. Connecting with other RI/LLs through data-sharing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contribution to the development of the Virtual Lab from which members will directly benefit from through using the platform for connecting with peer experts. Connecting with other RI/LLs through data-sharing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Finalising the Virtual Lab from which members will directly benefit from through using the platform for connecting with peer experts in the future network. Connecting with other RI/LLs through data-sharing.
Spaces/places	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Online Wider space is the environment of the pilot network itself 	Structured, facilitated hybrid environment within the pilot network (majority of members attending in-person, a few online).	Structured, facilitated hybrid environment within the pilot network (majority of members attending in-person, a few online).	Structured, facilitated hybrid environment within the pilot network (majority of members attending in-person, a few online).

2.2.4.2 Types of members involved

17 coordinators of the member agroecology living labs and research infrastructures were involved in the 1st pilot network meeting: 13 representing research institutes, one representing farmers/farmers advisors, two non-profit non-governmental organisations, one governmental organisation and one funding body.

11 members participated in the 2nd pilot network meeting: 6 representing research institutes, one representing farmers/farmers advisors, two non-profit non-governmental organisations, one governmental organisation and one funding body.

In the 3rd pilot network meeting, 12 members attended: 7 representing research institutes, one representing farmers/farmers advisors, three non-profit non-governmental organisations, and one governmental organisation.

15 members participated at the 4th pilot network meeting: 9 representing research institutes, one representing farmers/farmers advisors, three non-profit non-governmental organisations, one funding body and one governmental organisation,

It is important to note that the living labs and research infrastructures involved in the pilot network comprised a variety of stakeholders and users depending on their objectives (see Appendix 3). However, for the purpose of the pilot network, the best type of user is the one who runs and operates the initiative, who can give an insight into the activities, stakeholders, and internal process of the initiatives.

2.2.4.3 Format

During the 1st pilot network meeting, all workshops were conducted online using zoom due to the Covid-19 pandemic situation. The MURAL online platform was used for workshop tasks and exercises, the members were grouped into two breakout groups which helped to dive deeper into specific questions and topics.

WP3-5-6 co-creation workshops at the 2nd, 3rd and 4th pilot network meetings were held in a hybrid format allowing a few members to join via zoom and using MURAL to capture their inputs.

2.2.4.4 Results

WP3 co-creation workshops

Step 1: Co-creation of joint collaborative activities for the pilot network

The very first step to begin the co-creation of collaborative activities for the pilot network was the finalisation of pilot network expectations and needs. This process started with the pilot member selection in July 2021, when the members individually submitted their expectations and needs in writing. The validation exercise therefore built on these submitted expectations and needs which were reviewed and further refined by the members. Then, they created and decided on a ranking list of expectations and needs:

Expectations (in order of importance):

1. Knowledge exchange/ knowledge sharing/co-creation between LLs and RIs: Sharing challenges, best practices of living lab models, getting to know/more effectively implementing the co-creation process and data sharing among LLs or RIs seemed important.

2. Future collaboration in international research projects on agroecology: To create a platform for members to find each other with the goal of potentially applying for funding together.
3. Training the members in (1) new methodologies and approaches for agroecology transition and (2) how to share agroecology expertise with regions and countries which are not yet engaged.
4. Networking: To link up with other organisations with similar goals and profiles across Europe to pool resources and to extend members' network.
5. Testing and experimenting the tools and knowledge developed during ALL-Ready: having capacity building and training on becoming LLs/RIs.
6. Ensuring an active role for the members in the future Partnership: by honing members' skills in relation to agroecology transition or on how to run/develop AE RIs/LLs.
7. Discovering new agroecological practices.
8. Developing co-creatively common activities and to set agroecology research topics/priorities for the network: by also choosing the trending topics for agroecology transitions.

Needs (in order of importance):

1. Creating and maintaining an enabling environment for the pilot to exchange experiences and best practices: including sharing of information on coming conferences, relevant events, creation of bibliography database.
2. Ensuring access to stakeholders across the EU (farmers, agri-tech companies, and policy makers) through the pilot network.
3. Keeping the interest and trust ongoing between the members and ensuring the future involvement of the members in the future partnership by strengthening international collaboration to build capacity.
4. Empowering members to adapt transdisciplinarity in their LL/RI activities.
5. Building confidence and trust among the pilot members during the project.
6. Having a common agenda of agroecology research priorities with an LL and RI approach.
7. Looking at the possibility to replicate member AE LL/RI results/methods in other pedoclimatic and socio-economic contexts.

8. Evaluating activities linked to the co-creation process.

Figure 6. Mural validation exercise on the expectations of the pilot network

Then, the collaboration potential and joint network activities were mapped by the members in three main steps, building upon one another using validation, mapping and match-making methods as presented in Figure 6.

Figure 7. Three steps and corresponding methods used in joint network activities workshop

As a result of the exploration of agroecology interests of the members, 21 topics emerged, out of which **sustainable soil management, sustainable cropping/animal systems and digitisation in agroecology** were the most addressed among the member LL/RIs. There were a few topics that were limited to the scope of some members like rotational grazing, antimicrobial resistance, or non-food/feed supply chains.

Table 7 summarises the most common agroecology topics and the members engaged in these topics. However, challenges that individually affect members were separately listed in **Appendix 4**.

Table 7. Common and individual agroecology interests of the members

Agroecology LL/RI interests	Engaged Members
Sustainable soil management, soil carbon sequestration (regenerative agriculture)	CROPSYS, CarbonFarm, LLAEBIO, ÖMKi, Innovative Farmers, AAFC, ZAPVS, OasYs, ISF
Sustainable arable cropping practices	CROPSYS, CarbonFarm, LLAEBIO, ÖMKi, Innovative Farmers, AAFC, ZAPVS, OasYs, Occitanum, Organic RDD
Digitisation in agroecology, application of ICT tools for knowledge sharing among farmers	Occitanum, Guadalinfo, LifeWatch, Innovative Farmers, AAFC, ISF
Chemical pesticide-free plant protection	Carbonfarm, ÖMKi, ZAPVS, OasYs, Innovative Farmers
Agroforestry	Innovative Farmers, CarbonFarm, OasYs, LLAEBIO, Organic RDD
Agroecology market development	ÖMKi, Guadalinfo, ROADMAP, Innovative Farmers
Short and resilient food supply chains	ÖMKi, Innovative Farmers, ZAPVS
Mixed crop-dairy system and animal welfare, animal nutrition	Innovative Farmers, OasYs, ROADMAP
Food nutrition and health	Guadalinfo, ROADMAP, Innovative Farmers
Sustainable water use and management	Occitanum, OasYs, Innovative Farmers
Organic farming	LLAEBIO, ÖMKi, Organic RDD
Moving from practice-based thinking to systems thinking for agroecology	LLAEBIO, OasYs, AAFC, ÖMKi
Landscape management	ZAPVS, LifeWatch
Sustainable management of genetic resources	ÖMKi, Innovative Farmers
Making new crops acceptable by farmers and consumers (e.g., soybean, grains, legumes)	CROPSYS, Innovative Farmers
Using renewable resources in agroecology practice	Occitanum, Innovative Farmers
Culturally appropriate crops (especially with indigenous communities)	Innovative Farmers, AAFC

During match-making, members listed the most prominent agroecology-related research activities and challenges in relation to the previously noted agroecology interests. They also

had to highlight which of their activities they like to put forth for future collaboration, then make matches with other members' activities where they see cooperation potential.

The aim was to achieve a better understanding among the members about each other's LL/RI activities while mapping the cooperation potential among them to prepare for future collaborative activities.

Table 8 summarises the challenges that are common among some members, with **funding of LL/RI activities, improving end-user and stakeholder engagement** and **data management** being the most prevalent challenges.

Table 8. Common challenges of the pilot members

Common Challenges	Affected Members
Tightening the links between the stakeholders with the initiative (stakeholder engagement researcher motivation, sharing knowledge); encourage end-users (primarily farmers and smaller companies) to take part, to define activities	Organic RDD, LLAEBIO, CROPSYS, ROADMAP, ZAPVS, Innovative Farmers, Occitanum, Guadalinfo
Funding of the LL/RI activities; how to fund farmers for their expertise and on-farm experiments	LLAEBIO, ZAPVS, CROPSYS, Innovative Farmers, ÖMKi
Managing data within LL/RIs and lack of data sharing and use of data platforms	Occitanum, ZAPVS, AAFC, ÖMKi, LifeWatch
LLs is new to researchers, not really known in agriculture and among stakeholders – addressing the reluctance to cooperate	Organic RDD, ÖMKi, AAFC, Guadalinfo, Innovative Farmers
Maintaining/improving management practices (in relation to intercropping, weed management, soil quality) and outputs (yields)	Carbonfarm, OASYS
Moving from practice-based thinking to system thinking	AAFC, Organic RDD, LLAEBIO
Documenting and measuring (climate) effects of treatments, practices	Carbonfarm, AAFC

The definition of challenges, whether common or individual, reflect the problems that member LL/RIs face in their everyday operations. In order to meet the expectations of the pilot network, the network can act as a medium to address some of these challenges through collaborative activities.

As results of the match-making exercise, five main collaborative themes emerged each having specific activities: **(1) collaborative research to test specific agroecological practices with farmers through field trials/experiments, (2) collaboration for knowledge exchange and information sharing, (3) collaboration in long-term monitoring of agroecosystems, (4) advice for evidence-based agricultural policy development and (5) facilitation of EU project proposal development.**

Appendix 5 depicts the five collaborative themes and their connection to the common challenges, while **Appendix 6** details the specific activities with collaborators within the five collaborative themes.

After individual match-making, using mapping methodology, members further explored joint network activities that they would like to see implemented on the whole network level which will support the collaborative activities in the duration of the ALL-Ready project. Four main supportive joint network activities emerged which are listed below:

1. Creating and maintaining a platform (online) for members for sharing knowledge and methods for participatory approaches and information:
 - Building a library of best practices/examples/tools for knowledge sharing (esp. with farmers outside of the LLs) and for co-creation.
 - Creating a contact network of scientists/researchers interested to work on agroecology on various pedoclimatic and agronomic contexts.
 - Sharing relevant events about AE LL/Ris.
 - Organising regular updates (email) on Horizon Europe calls and consortium construction.
 - Developing common capacity-building materials.

2. Measuring and evaluating the impact of the pilot members' activities, research:
 - Developing a strategy to design the minimum indicators for assessing AE transition that will help the LL and RI governance and accounting for local specificities.
 - Developing indicators or methods to assess resilience in pilot members' agroecological systems.

3. Forming thematic working groups within the pilot network based on the collaborative themes

4. Organising workshops (co-design with members) to discuss very practical challenges:
 - GDPR/Data Management - how to best implement sharing of data coming out of living labs which could be useful for other databases/knowledge hubs.
 - Best practice around facilitating useful conversations between groups of farmers and other stakeholders on innovation needs & ideas.
 - Maintaining of living labs - how to avoid farmer dropout, learning workshops on common challenges when running a LL.
 - Product development.
 - Dealing with staffing changes in living labs (e.g., researchers/facilitators) - how to manage that transition & maintain group cohesion (between farmers and stakeholders, researchers, facilitators, etc.).

Step 2, 3 and 4: Operationalising the collaborative themes and the action plan of the pilot network

During the 2nd pilot network meeting, members revised the five collaborative themes and subtopics (developed during the 1st pilot network meeting) and modified them according to feasibility of the ALL-Ready project's time and capacity's constraints. Specific activities and tasks were formulated for the newly formed collaborative themes and responsible pilot network members were collectively assigned to each specific activity. Finally, the members prioritised the tasks.

As result of the discussion, **3 collaborative themes** were formed by merging collaborative themes 1 (Collaborative research to test specific agroecological practices with farmers through field trials/experiments) 2 (Collaboration for knowledge exchange and information sharing) and 3 (Collaboration in long-term monitoring of agroecosystems).

Pilot members agreed that field research and monitoring exercises cannot be planned and conducted in a frame of this CSA project. So, the pilot network needed to focus on building a structured knowledge and experience sharing environment where all member's results, data, research gaps, methods related to agroecology could be collected and shared. Therefore, creating space not only for documenting, but learning from one another. The original action plan can be found in **Appendix 7**.

During the 3rd pilot network meeting, members updated their action plan (new members expressed their interests in contributing to the task realisation) and added some new tasks. The updated action plan is detailed in **Appendix 8**. After the 3rd meeting, there were still two updates to the action plan, one in March 2023 and the last one at the 4th pilot network meeting. The last version of action plan and all the tasks completed are summarised in Table 9.

Collaborative theme	Task	Responsible members	Completion
Collaboration for knowledge exchange and information sharing among AE LLs/RIs	T1. Collaboratively map and create an inventory of (1) what is being tested right now (agroecological practices) in each LL/RI; (2) what farmers interests are in each LL/RI (3) what results/data and knowledge gaps each LL/RI has; (4) what research needs LL/RIs have; (5) what type of testing methods LL/RIs use; (6) what type of method is used for knowledge sharing and engagement of stakeholders in LL/RIs and (7) long-term monitoring data collection results of RIs Format: Joint spreadsheet created on Sharepoint shared with members. All members fill in with their own inputs and data.	ÖMKI ÖMKI created the template spreadsheet and sent reminders to the pilot network to regularly fill out the spreadsheets All members Fill in the spreadsheet	Template was shared with the members and completed between February and April 2023. Uploaded and maintained in the Teams group.
	T2. Collect and show existing educational curricula involving precision agri-solutions from the members	PA4ALL	Information on educational activities in the member LL/RIs were collected in the inventory and shared with PA4ALL.
	T3. Communication, promotion of members' agroecology-related research, project results and knowledge e.g., via	ÖMKI Between January 2022-October 2023	Social media series on pilot members, dedicated pages on the webiste, member

	website, learning networks, social media, webinar series		news/update dissemination, event sharing
	T4.Organising learning roundtables on specific topics + capture and disseminate results in the wider community	Innovative Farmers CarbonFarm ÖMKi AAFC Between June – December 2022	2 roundtable sessions were organised (with members) at the 2nd and 3rd pilot network meetings.
	T5.Evaluation of co-creation and co-design experiences in the pilot network	ÖMKi Ecologic	Evaluation questionnaire was co-designed together with the members in April, then it was completed by them between April-May 2023. The results of the questionnaire were shared and further discussed at the 4th pilot network meeting.
	T6.Recommendations on how to increase the size/scale of the pilot network (upscaling)	All members	Based on the results of the evaluation of the questionnaire a group discussion was dedicated to making recommendations for the future network at the 4th pilot network meeting.
Facilitation of networking for future research collaboration	T7.Prepare synergies between the strategic research and innovation agenda of the AE Partnership and the needs and aims of the LL/RI network	ÖMKi	AELLRI SRIA was shared, the deadline for comments was early October 2022.
	T8.Set up a small group within the network that monitors and selects relevant calls for proposal development, and (1) circulates these in the pilot network, and (2) facilitates partner matchmaking for collaboration on proposals.	Biobase ROADMAP ÖMKi LifeWatch	The group was set up, first meeting took place at the end of September 2022. The group finished screening relevant calls, and a screening spreadsheet was shared in February 2023 with the members. Each member completed the excel table by June 2023 and it became available for the network.
Raise awareness about the pilot network	T9.Raise awareness about the pilot network on a national and EU level	All members	Booklet on the ALL-Ready pilot network was developed together with the members between May-September 2023. The booklet was translated into

			7 languages and widely shared through consortium partners and pilot members. It was officially presented at the Final Conference in Brussels.
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Table 9. Completed action plan of the pilot network

Learning roundtables

There was a clear need from the very beginning (1st pilot network meeting) for organising recurring learning workshops for the members focusing on very practical LL/RI challenges. Therefore, from 2nd pilot network meeting onwards, so-called Learning roundtable sessions are conceptualised and organised together with the members around a specific topic important for the member to help them learn from each other's expertise and facilitate sharing of experiences.

Learning roundtable 1 aimed at share inspiring examples of co-creation methods and involving stakeholders and to help members to find solutions to their related issues and challenges through peer-to peer support and advice.

Innovative Farmers and AAFC presented about the co-creation practices used in their LLs. Then, the members were grouped into two groups. In each group, there were one facilitator, one notetaker and one lead peer. The task was the same in the two groups: Identify and share problems and challenges that members face in relation to co-creation and involving stakeholders, then find solutions together to the identified problems.

Group A

Members: AAFC, LLAEBIO, ROADMAP, CarbonFarm, Biobase

Problems
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gap between scientists and farmers and also between co-creative approaches and linear knowledge sharing (researcher-advisors-farmer). Scientific needs are not always compatible with farmers' needs. • Constraints of setting up experiments on farm (infrastructural, equipment related problems, impact on profitability) • Constraints of different timeframes: Researchers interested in setting up and documenting long-term experiments while farmers are in for a short-term gains • Not all stakeholders and end-users understand the problem and challenges in the same way (e.g. not everybody convinced that pesticides or antimicrobials should be reduced) • Complexity and systemic nature of barriers • Small agroecological farms are more present in the EU, therefore there is little room to test. Does size play a role ? • How the set-up of the LL/RI should be organised?
Solutions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research and practical needs need to be combined, by bringing together farmers and researchers to share challenges, expectations (creating a network) • Setting up complementary fields : similar or the same experiments are set on multiple farms. What did these farmers learn after the experiment ? • Creating a shared understanding of the problem by stakeholders, mainly discussing the impacts of agroecological solutions on profit. • Size plays a role in experimentation, some innovations are easy to adapt on small scale (advantage), but difficult to scale up (disadvantage).

- Identifying the role of each stakeholder and partner involved in LL/RIs and respect their expertise is important.

Group B

Members: Innovative Farmers, ÖMKi On-farm Living Lab, Occitanum, ILifeWatch

Problems
<p>Motivation of stakeholders and end-users:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long-term participation of partners: issue of farmer dropout and managing big fluctuation of stakeholders, change of hearts and high expectations, not having formal contracts • Lack of knowledge and practice among farmers in data handling • Time constraints to communicate in detail with all stakeholders (due to overloaded researchers) • Are researchers the right persons to communicate with everyone? Should communication, engagement and facilitation be the role of a specific person with the right skills? But in many cases LL/RIs cannot afford to hire facilitators.
Solutions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offer farmers and stakeholder long-term, written agreements with clearly formulated benefits and expectations, terms and conditions. • Constantly remind the stakeholders of the added value of the collaboration • Include evaluation cycles into the engagement or research/innovation process • If possible involve professional facilitators (hire them) for communication, and engagement. If not possible, explore the option of training researchers to take up this skill.

Learning roundtable 2 was built on one of the problems emerged during Learning roundtable 1: gap between scientists and farmers and also between co-creative approaches and linear knowledge sharing (The members voted beforehand on the most important problem they want to find a tool to.) The aim of this session was to inform the members about three practical tools for co-creation and stakeholder engagement to address the gap between scientists and farmers that they can use in their own LL/RIs, and to learn and reflect about the implementation and usage of these tools through situational exercises.

The LIAISON¹ co-creation toolkit focusing on three tools were presented:

1. Ground Rules: Identification of Opportunities and Challenges of Agreement-based Cooperation,
2. Needs Register: Recording Stakeholders Needs & Assessing Responsiveness
3. Speed boat: Clarifying and agreeing on the big idea together practices used in their LLs.

Then, the members were grouped into three groups, each having different scenarios. In each group, there were one facilitator, one notetaker, and members were randomly assigned to groups where each of them impersonated a particular LL/RI actor of their choosing (farmers, researcher, advisor, policy maker etc.). After having discussed and clarified the scenarios, the task was the same in all groups: members had to use the co-creation tool assigned to their group with the help of the facilitators to address the given scenario.

¹ <https://liaison2020.eu/>

Using the carousel method, members switched groups twice (facilitators stayed) and repeated the task but now using another co-creation tool. In this way, all members had the opportunity to try out at least two co-creation tools. The results of the situational exercises are detailed in **Appendix 9**.

During Step 4, the members also evaluated their pilot co-creation experiences and came up with recommendations for upscaling pilot activities in the future network. The analysis of these activities are detailed in Section 2.2.6. and Chapter 3.

WP5 co-creation workshops

Step 1: Capacity building programme: Exploring the competencies and skills for transition to agroecology and to run LL/RI

The main competencies for AE transition were explored, first, with the members focussing particularly on skills unique for a coordinator running an AE LL/RI. For some, the skills necessary to facilitate an AE LL or an AE RI do not differ from the skills to facilitate any other RI or LL.

Six main competency categories for agroecology transition emerged from the inputs:

1. Leadership & agility competencies :
 - watch over the mission and vision of the LL/RI and managing conflicting demands from the outside (the achievement of the goals defined together, bridge small daily actions to the overall goal of agroecology transition, not be overwhelmed by contradictory demands),
 - encourage others to get things done,
 - encourage people to join the LL (e.g., how to get some people on board of the LL, very specifically policy makers and social scientists),
 - delineation of responsibilities,
 - decision-making.
2. Organisational competencies
 - planning and time management,
 - documentation skills,
 - ability to change plans.
3. Networking competencies and actor knowledge
 - ability to build relationships,
 - listening skills,
 - knowing your stakeholders (understanding others strengthens participant involvement),
 - important to include social scientists to recognise opportunities to make or take roles in the LL,
 - communication skills.
4. Facilitating competencies :
 - internal conflict management especially regarding different views on agroecology of different members in the living labs,
 - active listening,
 - forward thinking and ability to make synthesis,
 - identify key challenges and opportunities,
 - be able to bridge between different actors from various backgrounds and thus different ways of thinking,
 - understand co-design methods,
 - facilitate user-drive process,
 - make a shared goal,

- methodological skills,
 - in-depth knowledge about processes.
5. Personal skills : encouraging others, people skills ; acting as a team player ; positive and constructive mindset
 6. Systems thinking : to be able to think across disciplines (natural vs. social sciences) and have a systemic approach.

Specific knowledge of both research and practical farming skills of the sectors. The coordinator needs to have a very good overview of agroecology and what it is about.

Then, important competencies were mapped for actors in AE LL and/or RI. Specific competencies were mentioned only for two groups of actors:

For farmers, it is important to develop the skill of “public speaking” (e.g., when they are interviewed). Furthermore, curiosity and patience are important in agroecology transition.

For researchers, the ability and willingness to conduct good research in an environment of change and innovation is important. They should understand ‘how to set up experiments in real-life context’.

More competencies were added, but not specified for a certain actor in the LL/RI:

- Communication and networking skills: collaboration and active listening.
- Personal skills: openness, holding back solutions before defining problems, team player, flexibility, willingness to allocate time for longer period.
- Engagement for the network.
- Systems thinking.
- AE principles and practical AE knowledge.
- Technical experience.
- Digital competencies.
- Knowledge of innovation management.
- Knowledge of risk management.
- Social sciences.

Pilot members also summed up the competencies that are well developed in their LLs or RIs. These member specific competencies are listed in **Appendix 10**.

To focus the capacity building programme on competencies that AE LL and RI want to develop or further upgrade, the members were asked to identify their actual needs for competencies that need to be developed for their initiative. These needs are listed below:

- **Business and marketing skills** can be achieved through involving an external expert for this role or by developing this skill internally.
- **Social and economic sciences**

Better understanding of socio-economic aspects like food sovereignty, farmers’ income, or difficulties of access to lands needs to be applied in LL/RIs which are majorly organised from the perspective of natural scientists who don’t know anything about the complex reality farmers have to deal with. Also, recognising the importance of human/social dimensions of innovation and adoption is just as important.

- **Data management**
- **Ability to diversify funding options**
- **Systems thinking**

Systems thinking is needed for dealing with complexity. Systems thinking is needed to approach agroecology not as a set of single practices but as a systems approach. For example, farmers mention that they do not adopt practices but work in a farming system. Researchers are sometimes very much focused on a particular topic/practice or scientific discipline but do not see how this might benefit or fit agroecology transition as a systems approach.

- **Design thinking** can help people to deal with the various knowledge (e.g., scale, sub-systems, etc.).
- **Facilitation skills and co-creation methods**
Development of skills and knowledge on how to set up experiments together in an atmosphere of confidence or how to start and set up a LL. Some challenges were mentioned that might hamper good collaboration in a co-creation setting. One challenge is to set up new collaborations to integrate additional expertise within the LL (e.g., including people as facilitating interaction between research and practice, including other scientific disciplines in the LL among which political sciences, social sciences, etc.). Further challenges are how to stimulate interaction between these different stakeholders and how to communicate with all different stakeholders (e.g., policy makers).
- **More ecological knowledge** and background for different kind of stakeholders, especially the farmers and policy makers if we want to move agroecology forward.
- **Skills/methods for monitoring/measuring carbon sequestration and GHG emissions**

The last part of the workshop investigated which role a network of living labs and research infrastructures can play in relation to building capacities. The roles highlighted by the members are detailed in **Appendix 11**.

Step 2: What competencies and skills can a European Network improve? Prototyping the capacity building programme

Building on the results of Step 1, the WP5 team put together a capacity building plan containing ideas for content and forms.

At the 2nd pilot network meeting, members prioritised the most important contents for the prototype programme and suggested suitable formats as well. The result of the prioritisation exercise can be seen on Figure 8.

Figure 8. Results of prioritisation of content and format for developing capacity building material

There were 5 major themes summarising the needs for capacity building material (knowledge on AE research, agroecology practical farming skills and knowledge, what agroecology is about, systems thinking and interdisciplinarity and understanding co-creation). For 4 of the 5 themes at least 1 vote was given. No votes were given for 'systems thinking and interdisciplinarity'. For only 2 of the more specific topics within the more general themes, at least 3 votes were given: knowledge on socio-economic assessments in agroecology-related research (knowledge on AE research as general theme) and setting up living labs (understanding co-creation as general theme).

Regarding the form of the capacity building material, it is not entirely unexpected that preference strongly depends on the content. For example, for facilitation skills, the preference is for a training course (online or in person), whereas for e.g., agroecology practical farming practices, demo events (farm visits), videos, and a bibliography database) are preferred.

For 'knowledge on socio-economic assessments in agroecology related research', participants indicated that a peer-to-peer learning activity just as e-course would be appropriate. For setting up living labs, participants indicated that a workshop, a library of best practices, just as a peer-to-peer learning activity would be appropriate. Irrespective of the topic, peer to peer learning and other interactive forms are most popular as forms for capacity building material. Forms as database, toolkits and factsheets didn't receive any votes.

Step 3: Co-designing the capacity building Training items

Building on the results of Step 2, the WP5 team shortlisted competency areas and training topics that are to be addressed in the capacity building programme:

1. Common understanding of agroecology,
2. Agroecology practical farming skills and knowledge
3. Knowledge on agroecology research
4. Systems thinking; and
5. Understanding co-creation

WP5 also conducted a data collection, which involved the ALL-Ready partners in the gathering of training materials and resources for all the above competency areas. The collection of training materials and resources clearly demonstrated that there already exists a large number of materials for the first 3 competency areas mentioned above, but that resources do not appear to be as accessible for the last two (systems thinking and co-creation). As such, a 3-pronged CPB prototype was proposed to the pilot network during the 3rd pilot network meeting. The proposed prototype aims to make good use and leverage existing resources while filling the gaps in training resource availability:

1. Build a master database of training materials and resources which would cover each of the five competency areas and which would present the materials in a user-friendly, highly customisable format using filters;
2. Create a new training on Systems Thinking which would include a basic course in addition to one or more exercises adapted to agroecology cases of pilot network members; and
3. Develop a 4-module course on understanding co-creation and living labs (see Figure 9 for the module details).

Agroecology practical farming skills and knowledge						
Format (video, e-course, database, etc)	Material description	Target audience	Language availability	Duration to view / review material (mins)	Material Owner (your organisation or another)	Link to ressource
Video recording	Playlist on soil health practices in organic and agroecological farming (half in HU with subtitles, the other half in EN)	Farmers	HU, EN	av. 30 min/video	ÖMKI	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9SM8IQCrajM&list=PLAKR11cz4fO.jHAOn9RthurPXIXQMawzT
Video Recording	Playlist on proper seed treatment, storage and seed saving (half in HU with subtitles, the other half in EN)	Farmers, seed companies	HU, EN	av. 15 min/video	ÖMKI	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8SbflQwwQ5A&list=PLAKR11cz4fOKg_j6rBBorMASbutedybf5
Video Recording	Videos consisting a wide range of organic and agroecological practices from crop production, animal husbandry, farm/food chain management etc.	Farmers, food chain companies	EN, FR, HU, IT, DE, ES, BG, FN, CZ, ET, LT	av. 15 min/video	Organic Farm Knowledge Platform	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCKA7iMg-4SxmWbxYQzfjEW
Publications	Downloadable publications on various organic farming practices and techniques from crop production, cover cropping, apiculture, viticulture to horticulture	Farmers	HU	90 min	ÖMKI	https://www.biokutatas.hu/hu/webshop/index/kiadvany/

Figure 9. Extract of the table of collected CB materials

After the presentation of the first CBP prototype, participants had to identify gaps in the prototype. The following gaps were highlighted:

Practical farming skills: Members requested that a farm performance enhancement platform (a Wikipedia-style website on farming practices, events, researchers, farmers), a toolbox within the IPM works project on IPM materials from 5 different database, a calendar for practical events should be added. Also, exchange with AKIS, and related projects should be included.

Common understanding of agroecology: LLAEBIO signaled that they have a ppt explaining AE with examples (NL) which can be added to the CBP. Members highlighted the AE should be illustrated with scientific proof, showing quantitative results and the economics of agroecosystems would be important, just as merging knowledge for researchers, farmers, LLs, and all pilot levels.

Knowledge on AE research: this part should be strongly linked with AE practical farming skills and overlaps with other databases, e.g., organic farm knowledge should be avoided. Organic Eprints, EU Farm book, filters/keywords on practical manuals, methodologies, end-users of the resource, AE concept, principles and the language of the tools should be added to the CBP.

Co-creation: ALL-Ready has already established an ecosystem of actors of co-creation which should be used. Theoretical background docs, templates to evaluate how the LL went, to arrange effective farmer-to-farmer, knowledge exchange events, a media kit for creating farming ambassadors, a toolbox with practical participation examples, a workshop to address challenges of the network members as they arise, and the best tools of the LIAISON project should be added.

Systems thinking: A specific course or a training is very much needed by the members.

Step 4: Capacity building training

After co-designing the programme content, 4 training modules were held for the pilot network members between March-June 2023:

- Module 1: provided them with an overview of living lab basics, governance models, and the business models of living labs.
- Module 2: focused on the management of living labs.
- Module 3: focused on commonly used tools and methods in each phase of innovation management as well as facilitation techniques.
- Module 4: focused on systems thinking.

All training modules were specifically targeted to LL/RI facilitators, but the systems thinking

Figure 10-11. A selection of photos taken during the interactive activity

training was also particularly designed for researchers in agroecology transition.

Key discussion points from the training module included:

- Insights into the principles, methodologies, and tools that can be used to effectively enact living labs' open innovation in agroecology.
- Overview of living labs' innovation management processes, panel management, pilot management processes & mapping canvas, and impact assessment methods.
- Commonly used tools and methods in each phase of innovation management.
- Showcase specific agroecology examples and case studies to highlight the application of co-creation and real-life experimentation in sustainable farming systems.
- Introduction to multiple facilitation techniques for capturing user insights and needs in agroecology projects and for problem-solving to agroecology challenges.
- Group discussion and exercises: participants split into groups to practice some of the techniques shown in role-playing activities to practice and apply facilitation techniques, focusing on agroecology-specific scenarios and live interaction.

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Some participants shared their concerns regarding the application of the techniques with the stakeholders of their LL. It was agreed that the techniques need to be chosen according to the stakeholders' interests and needs.

Figure 12-13. Moments from the capacity building training

WP6 co-creation workshops

Step 1: Building the Virtual Lab

The following results emerged from the Virtual Lab co-creation workshop:

- a. Needs of the pilot network that can be covered by a Virtual Lab
 - Sharing knowledge, data, and results (quantitative and qualitative) on specific agroecological practices and best practices.
 - Sharing information on other Living Labs.
 - Saving data, research papers, information, and other types of files.
 - A place to collaborate as a network.
 - Others: Attracting scientists, sharing tools, knowledge sharing on competencies relevant for agroecology, linking experts with topics, including the 7S framework of ICT (Strategy, Structure, Systems, Shared Values, Skills, Style, and Staff), links with other databases through easy pipelines.
- b. Expected outputs of the Virtual Lab:
 - Geographic overview of the network and the main characteristics of the LL/RIs.
 - Overview on good agroecological practices and living labs/research infrastructures (e.g., a library of resources).
 - A dynamic and user-friendly platform for network members.
 - A searchable data platform.
 - A place to announce learning sessions.
 - Others:
 - A space to raise awareness of the data produced in research infrastructures.
 - A prototype that can be developed further by the Agroecology Partnership.

- Comprehensive data and knowledge space for future collaboration among living labs and research infrastructures.
 - A space that will bring together the entire network.
 - Communication and networking tools (e.g., chat function) should be used to ensure participation.
 - Guides on trial design for farmer-led/farmer-centric trials.
 - Media/videos about specific practices.
 - Experimentation capacities (with data).
- c. Kind of data to be shared by the members:
- Results from agroecology best practices – including location (i.e., a map of the network).
 - Challenges encountered and potential solutions.
 - Existing policies to support agroecology practices.
 - Results from on-farm trials (sensors, remote sensing, soil, water quality, yield, crop physiology) - aggregated or not.
 - Others: Decision making process and outcome, indicators that will help following the agroecology transition, data on research (scientific data on carbon assimilation in soils, yields and quality, biodiversity in soils and on the surface, emissions, and leaching, etc.)
- d. Barriers to implement the Virtual Lab by the members
- Standardisation methods and data formats across the Member States; diversity of methods and assumptions in the data/results shared; diversity of situations, categories, quality of data.
 - Scientific data embargo before sharing.
 - Ability to engage actors other than the researchers.
 - Continuously encouraging actors to share their data and information.
 - Ensure complementarity/interoperability with other existing platforms.
 - GDPR.
 - Others: Data citation, need to demonstrate added-value/specific outputs, lack of common design/methodology leads to seemingly similar datasets not actually being equivalent, the need for metadata about how the data were collected to help their interpretation, some research infrastructures or living labs already have a platform like this one, lack of human capacity to upload large amount of data.

Figure 14. Mural results about the brainstorming on the Virtual Lab characteristics to fit the pilot network members' needs.

Step 2: How can a virtual environment support a European Network? Functionalities of the Virtual Lab

Based on the outcome of Step 1, WP6 team identified and prioritised four different functionalities that were discussed with the members at the 2nd pilot network meeting:

- Visualisation of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures Maps.
- Visualisation of Agroecology Best Practices.
- Networking tools.
- File sharing.

The four functionalities were presented and followed by specific questions with the aim of getting a deeper understanding of why the tools are needed and the main characteristics they should have.

Visualisation of Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures. One of the most voted applications was the visualisation of existing Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures in a map. Different visualisations were presented. Members highlighted that this tool would be important to enhance peer-to-peer learning (by knowing what other members are doing, activities), a way to know specific topics and aims of the different LL, and to obtain key information from the network members. Members also requested that other elements should be visualised, like specific agroecology research topics (e.g., Nutrient management), the time component (years of experience) and farmer typology.

Visualisation of Agroecology Best Practices. The functionality was identified as key to exchanging knowledge and promoting agroecology transition, but it started a discussion on what can be considered a best practice and how to evaluate it. Different ways were presented from plain text description to more elaborated evaluations by using specific tools (e.g., FAO – Tool for Agroecology Performance Evaluation TAPE). It was agreed by the members to change the name of best practices to good or inspirational practices. Instead of focusing on the best practices, it would be important to identify what can be given and obtained from the network.

Networking tools: A tool in the form of a matchmaking and marketplace was provided. The tool can link living labs and research infrastructure users with their services and interest, using standard vocabularies (e.g., AGROVOC). The tool can help to create members' own networks or even make suggestions based on specific keywords. The tool was valued for the potential to identify future collaborations.

Repository tool: a specific tool was presented to save data, research papers, information and other types of files in the form of a repository. The different objects in the repository will be linked to the same tags included in the members' profiles.

Step 3: Discussing the Agroecology Virtual Lab - testing version

Drawing on the results of Step 2, the WP6 team developed a Virtual Lab mock-up (testing version) which was presented during the 3rd pilot network meeting. There are five main sections of mock-up were shown: **Login Page, Dashboard** (including tips and guide to use the platform, community events, collaboration status, messaging chat messages, matches and new members), **Marketplace** (includes search engine optimisation with elastic search technology where public funding, innovation programmes, public procurement, and challenges are aggregated), **Profile** and **Find users** (There are 4 directories for the space ecosystem: researchers, policy makers, innovation sector, citizens. In every directory, every member will find other members with clear information needed to quickly make a decision to connect to collaborate).

The members were introduced to the mock-up through a training to show how the AE Virtual Lab works. During the training, three journeys were organised to show the different functionalities. This training was supported by videos and participants were able to practice by themselves with the help of the facilitators.

After the training, the members highlighted some gaps and errors they encountered during the testing of the mock-up such as providing given vocabulary to prevent misunderstandings and facilitate matchmaking, improve messaging services to inform someone when it is offline, exploration of blockchain solutions for data management, including the database of capacity-building activities that have been developed in WP5 or explore automatic translation tools to take advantage of the EU-added value of the tool.

Step 4: Finalising the Agroecology Virtual Lab and discussing innovation, data and IPR management

The members finalised the Virtual Lab by validating the main functionalities, the onboarding process and how to promote the use of the platform, explaining in detail how coordinators can update the information about their living labs or research infrastructures, introduce events and news or promote collaborations and exchanges through the marketplace.

Proposed functionalities

Figure 15. Proposed functionalities and access from the dashboard

Then current practices and potential barriers were also discussed related to innovation management, open science/open data, and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) among the members of the pilot network. It turned out that innovation management processes are well represented in most LLs and RIs, formally or informally. The biggest barriers identified for innovation management are lack of resources and resistance to change. Regarding open science and open data, although most LLs and RIs have formal or informal policies or practices, less than half actively promote the use of open science and open data. They highlight the benefits of open science as enhancing research transparency and promoting wider dissemination of research findings. The main challenges in terms of open science and open data are data privacy and security concerns and the reluctance of users to share data. Finally, regarding IPR, only one third of LL/RIs consulted have formal or informal IPR policies and there is a lack of specific methods to foster and ensure proper IPR management. The discussion focused on the need to understand what data and open data and the difference

between different types of innovation (from social to environmental) is. Further analysis of the innovation management and IPR practiced in LL/RIs is detailed in D6.4

2.2.4.5 Feedback on the experiences

After each pilot network meeting, individual feedback calls were conducted with the members to gather the impressions and experiences of the members about the meetings. In addition, project partners also evaluated their experience about the workshops. The summary of the feedback can be found in **Appendix 12**.

2.2.4.6 Challenges

The challenges experienced during the four pilot network meetings are summarised in Table 10.

Co-creation workshop	Challenges
WP3 co-creation workshops	
<i>STEP 1: Co-creation of joint collaborative activities</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was difficult to translate and implement the mix of methods used during this workshop to an online format, which prevented obtaining detailed information on each member and to get to know each members' activities more in-depth. • The complexity of the workshop structure and methods was necessary to get the right information from the members, however it might have been difficult to understand and follow through for some. This resulted in some cases in the provision of inadequate or fragmented inputs by the members. • Finding ways to engage the members more interactively beyond the methods applied during these exercises.
<i>STEP 2: Operationalizing the collaborative themes + Learning roundtable</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Being a hybrid workshop, it was challenging to have free-flowing conversation with members joining online, and address their inputs. The same applies to the Learning roundtable, where one of the groups was hybrid. • The working time of the two groups was a bit underestimated, therefore there was not enough time to have in-depth discussion and the plenary reflection needed to be skipped as well.
<i>STEP 3: Pilot network activity update + Learning Roundtable</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Although, the Learning roundtable was planned for a 3 hours long period, still it was not enough to close with plenary reflections which would have been important about the usability of the tools.
<i>STEP 4: Joint reflection on pilot co-creation experiences</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No major challenge, just not enough working time to discuss all questions and issues in depth.
WP5 co-creation workshops	
<i>STEP 1: Exploring the competencies and skills for</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The abstractness of the competencies and vagueness of the future network made it difficult for the members to understand right away and

<i>transition to agroecology and to run LL/RI</i>	<p>provide their expertise and inputs. It also created situations when the facilitators had to explain and clarify tasks more than expected.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The participation and input provided by project partners, who are not pilot network members, was confusing for the members and for the facilitators during this specific workshop, which might result in some biased outputs. • The combination of too many questions for the pilot network members without a clear action plan explaining for which action their input is needed is challenging.
<i>STEP 2: What competencies and skills can a European Network improve? Prototyping the capacity building program</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Being only a 30 min session, there was essentially no time to have discussions and reflections, just the prioritisation exercises. • Difficult format to follow online.
<i>STEP 3: Co-designing the capacity building training items</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This session was organised late in the day, so after a long day of meetings, it was a bit difficult to keep the participants energised, so they were not able to participate fully in the conversations.
<i>STEP 4: Capacity building training</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The training modules were lecture-focused with very few exercises which may have caused some attention decrease. • Some of the trainer did not come from the field of agriculture and did not bring examples from agriculture, therefore the relevance of these modules were not aligned with members' expectations.
WP6 co-creation workshops	
<i>STEP 1: Building the Virtual Lab</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finding different tools and methods specific for LLs and RIs (and/or aligning them) that serve the better understanding and prototyping of the Virtual Lab. • Facilitation is better organised and remains balanced if working with more than one group. • Finding ways to engage the members more interactively beyond the mapping method applied during this workshop.
<i>STEP 2: How can a virtual environment support a European Network? Functionalities of the Virtual Lab</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Similarly to WP4 workshop, there was not enough time go through all the functionality related questions with the members and to have reflection at the end.
<i>STEP 3: Co-designing the capacity building training items</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The session leader could only join online which created some miscommunication with the members during the training.
<i>STEP 4: Finalising the Agroecology Virtual Lab and</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No major challenge, just not enough working time to discuss all questions and issues of IPR in depth.

Table 10. Challenges of the three co-creation processes

2.2.5 SWOT analysis of the co-creation methods used

Strengths
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Methods used make possible the collection and validation of a wide range of information and inputs and the creation of new ideas from the different LLs/RIs. • Methods used fostered the better participation and inclusion of all members. • Learning from shared inputs and experiences from the members not only contributes to the overall goal of the ALL-Ready project, but it might inspire members to experiment with similar or new ideas and adopt different LL/RI practices. • The methods used give the members a sense of ownership and decision-making about the pilot network, capacity building programme and the virtual lab tool. • The digital format of the methods makes the tasks, exercises, and participation measurable. • The digital format of the methods makes the workshop recordable and shareable therefore it can be revisited many times and evaluated more in-depth. • The results gained through the methods used help to design and build the next workshops and their methods. • Visual presentation of the inputs and ideas helped the better understanding and overview of the discussions and each workshop results for the members. • In-person format of the 2nd and 3rd pilot network meeting helped the efficiency of the methods (validation, prioritisation, peer assist or carousel) applied as they provided a more open and personal environment for discussion and greater involvement in exercises. • The peer assist method was particularly valuable to create space for free experience sharing among members in small groups – so, essentially, everyone had the opportunity to voice their insights. • The carousel was very appreciated for creating a dynamic environment for experiencing the usage of the different co-creation tools. • Always use agroecology-related examples when applying participatory or co-creation tools, methods, and training.
Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The methods used only make the gathering of inputs from the coordinators of LLs/RIs, but not from other stakeholders of each initiative, therefore the inputs collected can reflect one-sided experiences and opinions. • The use of some methods in an online format prevented to obtain detailed information from the members, often just ideas and half sentences via post-its, therefore they need to be revisited. • Online implementation of the methods lacks the in-person element which result in deeper discussions and better bonding between the members.
Opportunities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The members can bring in new ideas and ways for collaboration, knowledge-sharing, co-creation, and co-design and might contribute to shift from practice-based thinking to system thinking. • The feedback and debates received by the members will help them to evaluate their current LL/RI practices or ways of thinking and improve them. • The participation through the methods encourages networking among the peer members, which might lead to long-term cooperation.

- The different methods and mixture of methods with the inclusion of fun elements help members to not only focus on practical, professional improvement but also to enjoy the co-creation process.

Threats

- Lack of willingness to be engaged through the methods due to time and capacity restraints or funding/resources.
- Inadequate inclusion and involvement through the methods, and lack of proper input, data management and sharing among the members after the use of methods might lead to low participation during the next steps and mistrust.
- Complexity of some methods might lead to confusion among the members which prevents them from contributing in a meaningful way.
- Lack of inclusion of funny and new interactive elements during the methods might result in very dry co-creation experiences.
- Continuing the online use of the methods without any face-to-face interactions might lead to lower collaboration and co-creation potential, knowledge-sharing and quality input collection from the members.
- When a training or a method example is not adapted to agroecology (the participant's field of work), it risks being unattractive, less relatable, and often not understandable for the participants.

2.2.6 Evaluation of the pilot co-creation experiences

The evaluation of pilot experiences was conducted in two main phases:

(1) An evaluation questionnaire was co-design together with the members in mid-March 2023 asking about general participation experiences (e.g., satisfaction, highlights, weaknesses, benefits realised, suggestions for improvement) and involvement in the future network. The questionnaire was shared and completed by the members in April and analysed in May 2023. 11 pilot members (out of 20) answered the questionnaire.

(2) The results of the questionnaire were shared during a group exercise at the 4th pilot meeting and several unclear topics were discussed.

Results showed that 90% of the members have never been part of such a network before and they really felt part of the pilot network through the organised engagement and applied co-creation methods. Difficulties were mentioned regarding online meetings, which many found unfavourable, and which gave less space for interaction and group work compared to in-person events. Contradictory responses were given concerning the interaction between members. Some mentioned that these interactions were insufficient, and more interaction could have been organised in-between in-person meetings. While others emphasised the need to reduce interactions (online and in-person) in the future network, because the LL/RIs are busy with their daily work, and they should not be overwhelmed with meetings.

The following table summarises the most important responses regarding pilot network highlights and criticisms:

Highlights	Weaknesses
------------	------------

- | | |
|---|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical meetings and training sessions. • Timely and considerate outreach on project activities. • Excellent management, accessible and responsive communication. • The combination and diversity of practices and participants. • Facilitation of the meetings. • The joint co-creation activities. • The atmosphere. | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insufficient link to agroecological characteristics and lack of specific examples. • Lack of updates on the website and regarding LL/RI member profiles. |
|---|---|

Table 11. Highlights and weaknesses of the pilot co-creation experiences

One particular issue that the evaluation showed is the lack of emphasis on agroecology (as a set of practice) in the pilot network. To address this, members suggested to improve the capacity building programme with a training module that offers context-specific examples from the field of agroecology (such as challenges in resources and water constraints, plant protection techniques, etc.). The emphasis should be on action and challenges for how to move forward in the AE transition. Moreover, members mentioned that the discussions in the network often centred on how to set-up, manage and facilitate AE LL/RIs which is mainly important for the LL/RI coordinators. Members suggested that not only the experiences of coordinators, but insights from other AE stakeholders should be taken into consideration more directly in the future network (e.g., creating specific forums for farmers, advisors to directly channels their experiences into the network).

Summary of suggestions to improve experiences and future activities:

- In the pilot network, the focus was mainly on knowledge exchange, sharing experiences on co-creation, methods, LL/RI functioning, co-designing specific outputs of WPs and less on agroecology content. A greater emphasis should be put on discussing farming practices in agroecology and increasing the number of field visits in the future.
- Bigger emphasis should be given to AE LL/RI specific business model development, for example as part of the future network's work.
- Greater focus (e.g., trainings) on the synergies between RI and LLs and how they can complement one another.
- Bring more stakeholders e.g., policymakers and farmers, to the table, externally or through LL/RIs.
- Less meetings organised (max. 3 online and 1 meeting in presence/year).
- Include feedback loops about meeting agendas, they can be potentially co-designed by the members in the future.

Generally, the members were very satisfied with the work and time spent and dedicated to the pilot network and all respondents want to be part of the future network based on their pilot experiences.

Further analysis and synthesised lessons learnt in the pilot network are elaborated in D3.3.

3. Recommendations for upscaling the pilot network

Members also came up with upscaling recommendations, building on their individual LL/RI and pilot network experiences, that should be considered or used by the future European network to support the transition more effectively to agroecology by LL/RIs on the European scale.

The recommendations fall into three main categories:

a) Specific activities that should be scaled-up

These are activities and formats that were either considered very useful by the members during the lifetime of the pilot network or proven activities that members have knowledge of from their own LL/RIs and which therefore should be applied on a larger scale.

Recommendations:

1. Booklets, videos, case studies, webinars, and training materials are all important tools for scaling up. Therefore, a common network repository storing information on activities of all LL/RIs should be built together with a regular newsletter for the future network to find and share up-to-date and relevant information.
2. Put in place a system for formal onboarding, mentoring of new members and mandatory training process for newcomers.
3. Include more farmers, agronomists, and advisors in the network through the member LL/RIs or externally.
4. Keep the workshop formats and learning roundtables with all the co-creation methods used in the pilot network for the European network as well to maintain co-design, discussions and to stay connected.
5. Create LL/RI classification (accessible to everyone) that allows a better overview and exchange on specific topics. It might be useful to explore the creation of subgroups by regional and subregional challenges or thematic working groups that can support scaling up by sharing know-how and best practices.
6. Field visits are essential for scaling up, but combined with trainings might be more interesting and informative.
7. Trainings on how to set up, run a LL, how to engage stakeholders (agroecology LL toolbox) and how to improve LL/RIs (e.g., transdisciplinary approach, co-creation etc.) would be important.
8. Peer consulting (method) should be a regular online or offline occasion (one-on-one or group) in the future network where members can exchange ideas and experiences on specific issues of interest or problems.
9. Members highlighted that the Virtual Lab in its current form is too complicated and less usable for the members to be scaled up.

b) Building national networks of AE LL&RIs

This category details members' opinions and insights on the possibility of building national networks that can potentially support upscaling activities.

Members emphasised that AE, LL, and RI are fuzzy concepts, and it is important to protect these concepts against 'co-opters' while upscaling. In the perspective of the transition towards AE, it is difficult to exclude people, however the core principles should still matter, e.g., user-centeredness.

Recommendations:

1. Already existing, possibly certified LLs in a country should join forces to raise awareness about the importance of LLs in the transition and start to train initiatives with similar activities. (e.g., Greece and Hungary are currently doing this.)
2. Already existing living labs should focus on building cooperation and incorporating other groups in their internal networks.
3. Some countries expressed the need to organise national LL/RI networks while others are content with the currently available national structures. But all agreed that mature, well-known living labs can have a special role as 'lighthouses' at the country level to raise awareness and to train and educate national agri-innovation ecosystems about AE living labs and their role in the agroecology transition, therefore fostering national upscaling activities.

Some examples:

- Denmark: Members are not sure whether they need a national network because in their small country individual LLs work well and the diversity of stakeholders is high. Also, such a network needs management and continuous funding to maintain.
- France: There are several AE LL/RIs, however, the link between them is missing and they are not well connected. It would be useful to have a network that strengthens the links between French LLs and RIs.
- Switzerland: A network and Virtual Lab with key contact details and information on topics would help collaboration.
- Spain & Hungary: A national network would be important in order to connect, collaborate in participatory research and show the benefit of agroecology practices on a national scale.
- Flanders: LLAEBIO already integrates other LLs in Flanders, but not in connection with the Walloon region – language is a challenge to connect with French-speaking LLs.

c) Creating a testbed within the future network:

The idea of creating a similar testbed (like the pilot network) within the European network was raised by the members. The purpose of the testbed would be to co-create and implement thematic and cross-cutting agroecology research activities based on the interests of member LL/RIs, but on a much bigger scale – depending on the size of the network and the interest to join. But this testbed, functioning as a network within the network, needs to have the capacity to incorporate more LL/RIs from all Member States than the pilot network could do.

It is important to note that for upscaling activities the size of the future network is a key factor, which is currently unclear.

Further upscaling recommendations based on pilot network experiences that can be used by the European network are detailed in D4.2 and D4.3.

4. Next steps

As the work in the pilot network concluded with the end of the ALL-Ready project, there are two critical next steps:

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- The analysis of co-creation experiences and lessons learnt from the pilot network will be handed over to the coordinators of the AGROECOLOGY Partnership and its European network to guide and plan future co-creation activities of member LL/RIs. Accordingly, the results of this deliverable can be directly utilised and built upon.
- Ensure the involvement of the pilot network members in the future network by inviting them as the first cohort of official members at the launch of the European network in the first half of 2024.

5. Conclusion

This document gave an overview on the ALL-Ready pilot network, including its objectives, defining characteristics and activities and showcased its diversity through the presentation of all 20 members in detail, situating them in the framework of agroecology transition.

The deliverable provided a detailed description of the co-creation processes within the pilot network in WPs 3, 5 and 6 and an in-depth analysis on the experiences and methods based on the results of the four pilot network meetings. It is clear from the experiences that the involvement of all members in these processes facilitated learning from shared inputs and expertise that further inspired members to experiment with similar or new ideas, adopt different LL/RI practices or to assess their practices from a different perspective. The co-creation enhanced the sense of ownership and decision-making power of the members about the pilot network. It was widely acknowledged that the exercises done in the workshops supported networking and getting insight into the activities of peer members, which furthers long-term collaboration. However, the online format of some meetings (1st pilot network meeting) prevented the deeper discussion on specific common agroecology interests and negatively affected the quality of inputs and the forming of personal connections between the members. Managing time, the hybrid format and constantly finding new ways to engage the members more interactively remain notable challenges for the future. The use of complex methods should be avoided and rather application of short, but very simple tasks should be prioritised. Experience showed that monitoring and evaluation of the whole co-creation process is essential and needs to be planned from the beginning to improve co-creation processes along the way.

In addition, developing and maintaining a common vision and purpose among different stakeholders in the co-creation process, besides trying to find a solution to a specific problem, is one of the most important first steps to stimulate and involve participants. In the pilot network, the shared goal of pursuing a transition towards agroecology was a significant motivation for the members to get engaged in the process. It was widely acknowledged by the members at the end of the project that diverse local or national networks of individual AE LL/RIs should be strengthened to accelerate innovation. The network functioned successfully because strong linkages between different sectors, actors and perspectives were formed. Such connections are essential for ensuring that new ideas are quickly turned into tangible solutions, therefore facilitating rapid innovations. Moreover, co-creation requires careful planning, trust-building, and continuous communication to meet the needs of all stakeholders. Therefore, working with experts in co-creation and allocating appropriate resources is necessary to run such networks, especially the future European Network.

All these experiences coupled with upscaling recommendations are planned to be carried into the future European Network through the coordinators of the network and the pilot members and adapted according to its size, scope, and stakeholders.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Presentation of the pilot network members

Institute for Sustainable Food (RI)

Context

The Institute for Sustainable Food at the University of Sheffield was launched in 2019 and encompasses three research pillars to address the whole food system: plant production and protection; translational and transformative research, and food consumption, health and sustainability. Research conducted within the institute brings together researchers from multiple disciplines to understand and transform whole-system food production from field to fork.

Aim: To address the challenges of food security and sustainability.

Activities

- Regenerative agriculture and soil health
- Land use policy and practice
- Improving biodiversity on agricultural land
- Protecting crop plants against pests and diseases
- Carbon sequestration potential of agricultural soils
- Better nitrogen use efficiency in crops, to reduce fertiliser inputs on field
- Increasing food production in urban areas

Sir David Read Controlled Environment Facility
Source: <https://www.sheffield.ac.uk/sdrcef>

Participants

Researchers, farmers, industry stakeholders, policy-makers

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

The Institute for Sustainable Food seeks to discover new ways to understand the complexity within the food production system ‘from farm to fork’, addressing the agri-food system as a whole and not just in terms of its separate parts. Thus, integrating across the domains of production and consumption and embedding the needs of individual stakeholders from consumers and farmers to the wider business community, NGOs and government.

Our approach recognises that achieving a sustainable food future is as much a socio-cultural problem as it is technological, understanding the global nature of the food system while appreciating its impacts can be both local and global in scale.

Diagrammatic representation of the agri-food ecosystem. Modified from Horton et al. (2017) Food Security 9: 195-210. Source: <https://www.sheffield.ac.uk/sustainable-food/about/vision>

Achievements

- Working with more than 100 different industry partners from across the farm to fork spectrum, including policymakers.
- 145 research groups are working to address challenges to food security and sustainability
- The Healthy Soil, Healthy Food, Healthy People (H3) project is a £6m consortium grant funded from the Transforming UK Food Systems call, which will transform the UK food system from the ground up.
- The Desert Garden Appeal is a unique project born out of innovative Sheffield science that is giving families displaced by war the opportunity to grow fresh food in the desert using the most unlikely of materials – discarded mattresses.

LifeWatch-ERIC (RI)

Context

LifeWatch-ERIC as an international organisation is adding knowledge and deepening understanding on biodiversity organisation and ecosystem functions and services in support of our societies to address the key planetary challenges.

Aim: To supply e-Science research facilities to the European scientific community to support decision-making processes.

Participants

Researchers, data providers, public administrators, policy-makers

Activities

- Offering new opportunities for large-scale scientific development,
- Supporting knowledge-based decision-making for biodiversity and ecosystem management,
- Providing training, dissemination and awareness programmes,
- FAIR data share, visualisation and models.

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

Using an innovative methodology, a modular Virtual Lab will be developed, to provide e-Services, either individually or in any type of possible combination (integration) in order to offer access, management and analyses to a wide range of data.

Such a Virtual Lab facilitates exploring all the information collected from end-to-end in each of the processes and practices (from the data collected by sensors to the socio-economic ones). It will foster agroecology transition, through a co-designed and co-developed tool to improve the problem-solving capacity of researchers, SMEs and entrepreneurs, and providing evidence-based policy making capacities for government and funding bodies. Furthermore, citizen science activities are also planned.

CropSys (RI)

Context

Long-term experiment on organic and conventional arable cropping systems (CropSys) is running for 25 years and is based at the Department of Agroecology, Aarhus University (DK). It includes three experimental factors, has a factorial design, and is replicated in two blocks. The factors are cropping system (organic with grass-clover ley, organic with grain legume and conventional with grain legume), with and without cover crops, and with and without manure in the organic systems. Crops include cereals (barley, wheat, rye and oat) and grain legumes (faba bean, pea, lupin).

***Aim:** Exploring the possibilities for increasing soil fertility, productivity, and efficiency of arable cropping systems, by adopting different agroecological practices.*

Activities

- Crop diversification in time and space:
 - Different crop sequences with inclusion of grain legumes and ley,
 - Cover crops,
 - Intercropping.
- Maintaining and improving soil health.
- Reducing negative environmental consequences of agriculture.
- Local production of plant-protein.

Participants

Researchers, farmers, advisors, technology providers

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

There is a close collaboration with farmer advisory services, companies (e.g., for development of machinery and tools) as well as with ICROFS (International Centre for Research in Organic Food Systems). Together with these stakeholders, we organise several field days every year, with focus on different aspects. CropSys is used as a research platform by researchers and students with different expertise and scientific aims, allowing a comprehensive assessment of long- and short-term changes due to treatments and environmental factors.

Achievements

- Long-term data collected in a large database (which will be made more accessible).
- Established and new national and international collaborations.
- Funding ensured through continuous grant application efforts.

Centre for Circular Bioeconomy (RI)

Context

Aarhus University Centre for Circular Bioeconomy Production and Management of Agricultural Biomass (CBIO) is part of a research and development value chain for bioeconomy production systems and recirculation concepts, focusing on production of the raw material- biomass- for refining methods and on high-value products based on agricultural crops.

Principles & Values

CBIO supports scientifically the bio-based economy for replacing fossil raw materials with renewable plant-based materials, including for bioenergy production. Production and Management of Agricultural Biomass is the initial value within CBIO value-chain targeting refining of biomass.

***Aim:** Establishing and maintaining field trials for providing high-quality data from a plethora of agroecosystems, ranging from conventional grain crops to perennial herb crops and their combination, as well as data processing and results dissemination.*

Activities

- Establishment and management of field trials, including operations planning and management- sowing and re-sowing plants, fertilisation and irrigation, pests and diseases management, equipment installation, data collection and compilation.
- Visualisation, quality-control and analysing all the data from the field trials.
- Sharing new knowledge with the world scientific community and sometimes with the general public.

Participants

Researchers, farmers, advisors, industry stakeholders

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

CBIO is working on creating high-quality field trial locations with representative agroecosystems for monitoring and measuring to kick-start a biobased economy with sustainable high-value products such as proteins, polymers, and new chemical or biological components for industry.

Illustration: Kiril Manevski

Achievements

- Important science achievements within CBIO agricultural biomass research infrastructure tackle the agronomic and the environmental characteristics of the agricultural biomass targeting future biorefineries:
- Design agroecosystems with prolonged coverage of the soil with biomass, thereby balancing biomass production and nitrogen leaching.
- Agroecosystems of perennial herbs produce large protein yields as promising and local alternative to the environmentally-costly overseas export of soy for animal feed.
- Finding lower nitrous oxide emissions from agroecosystems of perennial herbs compared to annual crops, despite their intensive field management.
- Land conversion from annual to perennial crops could be the win-win strategy for soil carbon and nitrogen sequestration.
- Effect of crop season on nitrogen leaching and of biomass-protein link related to plant life duration.

LTSER Zone Atelier Plaine & Val de Sèvre (RI)

Context

LTSER Zone Atelier Plaine & Val de Sèvre (ZAPVS) was established in 1994 in nouvelle Aquitaine, having a very large diversity of landscapes. Zone Atelier was created in 2009 forming a network together with LTSER and Recotox.

***Aim:** exploring solutions with stakeholders (farmers, citizens, beekeepers, etc.) to develop resilient agricultural socio-ecosystem practices.*

Participants

Local public bodies and municipalities, Researchers/Research institutes, Farmers, Consumers/Consumer organisations, NGOs

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Activities

- Long term monitoring of biodiversity, ecological functions, land use and agricultural practices since 1994 for the oldest.
- Experiments at the landscape scale to understand the role of biodiversity in food production and farmers economic performance.
- Experimenting of nature-based and socioecological solutions, to foster agroecological solutions with farmers.
- Fostering the transformation of the agrifood system.
- Communication with local farmers and schools, national authorities and international community through publications.

REWET (RI)

Context

ReWet was established in 2021, in order to provide infrastructure at ecosystem scale to study the effect of rewetting drained agricultural and forest peatlands on greenhouse gas emissions (CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O) and fluxes of nutrients (P and N), dissolved organic and inorganic carbon (DIC, DOC). In Denmark 10% of the GHG emissions is a result of drainage of peatlands, the national 70% GHG reduction goal by 2030 cannot be achieved without rewetting a substantial area of drained peatland. ReWet will establish four observatories on agricultural and forest peatland sites. These observatories will serve as platforms for ecosystem monitoring, experimental research, technological development, and demonstration.

***Aim:** to facilitate climate-smart management and land use change related to agriculture and forestry on soils with high organic carbon contents*

Participants

National, regional and local public bodies/authorities, researchers, advisors, farmers, processors, SMEs, NGOs

Activities

The research infrastructure aims to cover the variations in Danish peatlands. ReWet will establish observatories on four different sites.

- Gas flux measurements
- Emissions of GHG (CO₂ and CH₄) monitored in larger areas (>1 ha) at all sites by EC systems to represent the fluxes at ecosystem scale.
- Hydrology and water quality.
- Measure energy, nutrients, biodiversity changes.
- Guidelines for land-use policy and practice.

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

The ReWet observatories strengthen the links between the restoration of ecological and biogeochemical functions of peatlands and the wider benefits this can provide to society. Using the ReWet observatories as part of wider living laboratories on wetlands, the results generated contribute to solving the mosaic of challenges in wetland restoration, raising public awareness of the importance of peatlands for nature, the environment and climate, and finally, translating these into a language that is understood within broader policy forums.

Achievements

- Local authorities, farmers and researchers are co-creating an overall landscape strategy in which a multifunctional land consolidation scheme, whereby wetlands under agricultural use, are exchanged for agricultural land in less sensitive areas.
- Eight ha of agricultural peatland is used for sampling and analyses of drainage water, measurement of greenhouse gas emissions, paludiculture, and the testing of light machinery by Aarhus University.
- A commercial company delivers wet meadow grass to a research facility for biogas production and will be involved in future production of grass for biorefining.

OasYs system experiment (RI)

Context

OasYs is an agroecological dairy cattle system aiming to be adapted to climate change. Redesigned through a collaborative approach, it is carried out as a system experiment at the farm scale in an INRAE facility located in a French plain area already affected by summer droughts.

***Aim:** Enabling farmers to live from their dairy cattle system in a context of climate change, while saving water and fossil energy resources and contributing to sustainable agriculture*

Activities

- Forage diversification,
- Year-round grazing,
- Browsed fodder trees,
- Integrated livestock breeding strategies,
- Multicriteria assessment.

Participants:

Researchers, farmers, advisor, industry stakeholders

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

OasYs is an innovative system redesigned through a collaborative approach with various stakeholders. It relies on an agroecological approach, based on the diversity of the system's components and their functions, and aiming to adapt a low-input farm to climate change. It is experimented at the farm scale on an INRAE facility. The forage system (90 ha) produces the fodder necessary to feed the dairy cattle herd (72 milking cows, and replacement heifers) without irrigation and with limited use of mineral nitrogen fertiliser, whatever the climatic hazards. The forage resources are diversified (including fodder trees) and priority is given to their grazing. The livestock breeding strategy is in coherence with the forage system, with two calving periods in spring and autumn, the extension of lactation length to 16 months and the three-way crossing of dairy breeds (Holstein, Scandinavian Red, Jersey). The system is evaluated in terms of its production performance, as well as its environmental and socioeconomic performance. It is a place for exchange with stakeholders.

Achievements

- The nutritive value of 31 tree, 14 shrub and 7 liana species has been assessed.
- Diversity of grazing resources enabled extension of grazing period.
- The increase of fat and protein contents offset the decrease in milk production.
- The system allowed 1.5 labour units to be remunerated at a rate equivalent to the income of two minimum wage earners.

EMPHASIS (RI)

Context

The European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) has identified "Plant Phenotyping" as a priority for the European research area, and EMPHASIS has been listed on the ESFRI Roadmap 2016 for Research Infrastructures. Since then, EMPHASIS has concluded its preparatory phase in 2021 and started implementation. Therein, ministry and scientific representatives from eleven countries discuss and decide on the strategic aspects of EMPHASIS operation as part of the EMPHASIS Interim General Assembly. In parallel, EMPHASIS runs pilot services intended to lead to the full EMPHASIS service portfolio once being operational. EMPHASIS enables researchers to use facilities, resources and services for plant phenotyping across Europe. Our vision is to help scientists better understand plant performance and translate this knowledge into application.

Aim: EMPHASIS aims to promote future food security and agricultural business in a changing climate by addressing the technological and organisational limitations of European plant phenotyping.

Participants

Researchers, scientists, policy makers

Activities

- EMPHASIS facilitates standardised and interoperable plant phenotyping in multi-environment field experiments through different field phenotyping services.
- EMPHASIS coordinates and support various training activities in plant phenotyping.
- EMPHASIS helps users to bridge the gaps towards a local information system following FAIR principles (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable), so their datasets can be used by a large scientific community.
- EMPHASIS works closely with the plant phenotyping community to develop Good Phenotyping Practices that will ensure experimental reproducibility and reusability of data.
- EMPHASIS aims to drive innovation in plant phenotyping technologies to ensure long-term sustainable excellence.
- The modelling online portal offers image analysis software tools, image data sets and plant models.
- The EMPHASIS Infrastructure Map provides an overview of plant phenotyping installations across Europe.

"Phenotyping for future
and more resilient varieties"
Oliver Klotz
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Germany

"Crystal ball peering into
the future of Plant Phenomics"
Angelo Perrotti
ARIA - Mediterranean Agronomic
Research Center, Italy

Achievements

- Yearly more than 100 farms take part voluntarily from the country.
- User testimonials of access to plant phenotyping facilities: https://eppn2020.plant-phenotyping.eu/Selected_Projects
- Deliverables from EMPHASIS preparatory project: <https://emphasis.plant-phenotyping.eu/outreach/publications/deliverables-surveys>

ÖMKi On-Farm Living Lab (LL)

Context

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**ALL-Ready - The European Agroecology Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network:
preparation phase**

D3.2 Reports of ALL-Ready Pilot Co-Creation Experiences – Report n.3 – 01 December 2023

ÖMKi on-farm living lab is an agroecology-focused nationwide participatory experimentation network that includes a variety of field trials and technology tests co-designed and co-implemented with farmers with the aim to improve and/or develop new organic/agroecological practices, products, technologies.

Aim: *Fostering scientific research on organic agriculture and contributing to agroecology transition in Hungary.*

Participants

Farmers, researchers, advisors, authorities, processors, retailers, consumers, and other industry stakeholders

Activities

Crop diversification for food system stability

- Ancient cereal variety tests and product development
- Landrace tomatoes - cultivation technologies
- Soybean in the crop rotation

Soil-building cultivation technologies

- Species-rich inter-row cover in vineyards and orchards
- Organic nutrient replenishment
- Herbicide-free tillage technologies (reduced-till, ground cover, etc.)

Precision farming solutions for organic agriculture

- Remote sensing for plant protection
- Sensors for developing customized feeding and disease prevention system

ÖMKi's on-farm network 2012-2018

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

The Lab combines two processes into one complex system, that finally results in product/service/technology development. The so-called 'on-farm method' is an open innovation process in itself, that is used by the ÖMKi Lab to improve agricultural production practices in real-life farm settings (on the farm). The research involves farmers (or other end-users) in all the steps, therefore they become active participants in the co-creation of the research from step 0. The real environment in every case is the actual farm of

the producer and the experiments are always adjusted to the farmers' production or environmental goals. As the Lab started to develop products, the on-farm method merged with the classical product development stages, thus creating its specific ÖMKi Lab product development process. In this process, the on-farm research is used to define and/or test agricultural product ideas and services and adjust them to a market gap. New product/service testing, development and improvement can also take place as a service of the Living Lab.

Achievements

- Yearly more than 100 farms take part voluntarily from the country.
- Introduction of organic bee health management against varroa mite.
- Variety tests and agrotechnical development in winter wheat, soya, potato and wine production.
- Number of technology and production guides for organic farming (tomato, grapevine, potato, fruit trees, soya bean etc.).
- Good information network among the stakeholders of each sector.
- Marketed products and services: Tomato landrace seedling package, Living interrow seed mixture, ancient emmer flour, organic advisory service.
- Opportunity to take part in EU research cooperation.

LLAEBIO - Living Lab Agroecology and Organic Agriculture (LL)

Context

The Living Lab Agroecology and Organic Agriculture (LLAEBIO), supports agroecological innovation as a lever in the transition to sustainable food and agricultural ecosystems in the region of Flanders (BE). This living lab brings together actors from the agri-food system with a shared interest in agroecology and organic farming to facilitate innovative research and to share knowledge and experiences. The overarching goal of LLAEBIO is to connect people, organisations, policy, science, and practice.

Principles & Values

From the beginning, LLAEBIO has used the basic ENOLL principles and components for living labs. These principles provide a steady compass for the members and their discussions and

practical activities. System thinking, the aim to join scientific and tacit knowledge, and strong stakeholder engagement and involvement are all seen as being indispensable to innovation.

***Aim:** Spread information, knowledge and expertise about agroecology and organic farming. Bring people together to facilitate mutual exchange of expertise and knowledge about agroecology and organic farming. Facilitate and support research and experiments on agroecology and organic farming.*

Participants

Researchers, farmers, advisors, industry stakeholders, teachers, policy makers

Activities

- Organisation of interactive and educational knowledge-sharing activities in order to:
 - strengthen connection between stakeholders,
 - enhance farmers' knowledge about agroecological practices and opportunities (preferentially via peer-to-peer exchange),
 - raise all other actors' awareness of the potential of agroecology,
 - bring scientific knowledge to experiences on the field and vice versa.
- Identification of knowledge and research gaps within agroecology and organic farming;
- Support for and/or development of project proposals, in which agroecology and/or organic farming practices are investigated according to the 5 operational principles of living labs as defined by ENOLL (multi-method approach, multi-actor participation, real life context, involvement of end-users, co-creation and openness) and a transdisciplinary systems thinking approach;
- Deepening of our knowledge of systems research.

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

Annually, working themes are chosen together with key stakeholders of the living lab as part of an interactive workshop. Temporary participative working groups, formed of volunteers who participate based on their interests, are established to define and develop activities and actions on these themes. Depending on the specific goals of the working groups and the groups being targeted, the best tools and working methods (field visits, webinars, round tables, etc.) are explored and chosen. The activities target all actors in the agri-food system with an interest in agroecology and/or organic farming, e.g., farmers (conventional and organic/agroecological), farm suppliers and buyers, food processors, consumers, researchers in different disciplines, extension workers, (farm) advisors, teachers, policy makers, NGO members, and the like.

Defining themes of interest with LLAEBIO members during an annual interactive workshop

Achievements

Sharing knowledge and connecting people

- 'LLAEBIO draait door' is a quarterly event that keeps members up to date about LLAEBIO activities and provides a forum to partners to share their needs or experiences in projects or other activities (<https://www.llaebio.be/output>).
- Webinars on themes of interest. One such webinar was on 'fair pricing' in response to a farmer's question. An exploratory system thinking exercise on that theme resulted in a series of 3 webinars with an exchange of theoretical and practical knowledge (<https://www.llaebio.be/output>).
- Webinar on sustainable soil management, with short videos of farmer testimonials (https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCkyum8O69TwK_xyHV8_Ls7A).
- Farm visits and demonstration days.
- An inspiration day for agricultural secondary school teachers to support teachers in introducing agroecology in education. We also contribute to courses on agroecology in higher education or post-school education.

Facilitation of innovative research

- Facilitation of the development of research projects by connecting (research) organisations or/and encouraging stakeholder engagement in projects.
- A shared PowerPoint presentation about the agroecology concept, with the aim of fostering understanding of the scientific foundations of agroecology. We also support the creation of a science-based agroecology think tank.
- Round table discussions to define research priorities together with the organic sector.

Occitanum (LL)

Context

Occitanum is an archipelago of 13 Living Labs deployed on different pedo-climatic and production sites across the Occitanie Region. These user-centred labs bring together all the local and regional stakeholders to develop innovative projects for a variety of agricultural and local food systems. Occitanum follows an original structure allowing flexibility and complementarity. It is based on seven open labs based on six production systems (beekeeping, orchards, vineyard, field crops, livestock, market gardening) and one on local supply chain. Each open lab is dispatched on different pilot sites, each with a different innovative project with its specific governance. General governance is managed through the core entity allowing for the general coordination, research and training actions, valorisation, and financial actions.

***Aim:** Deploying digital technologies to foster agroecology transition and regionalise food supply.*

Participants

Farmer communities, local authorities, agricultural development actors, AgTech firms, citizens as well as researchers, engineers, technicians, and academics.

Activities

- Establish and implement innovative projects:

- test new digital solutions in a real-world environment
- develop co-innovation with stakeholders
- Codevelop innovative methods,
- Foster involvement of AgTech Firms in open innovation processes,
- Develop multi-disciplinary research,
- Assessment of the potential of digital technologies used in Open Labs.

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

Different tools are used to get a good stakeholder participation and involvement:

- Regular meetings even during the Covid crises using participatory remote tools.
- Transparent and clear method called "service map" that allow to go from the stakeholder's need to the requirement for AgTech to develop new products.
- Call for interest to the AgTech enterprise to propose solutions to farmers.
- Development of robust protocols to evaluate innovative solution in real life.
- Training on AgTech to motivate the different stakeholders.

Achievements

- 49 partners involved,
- 25 emerging innovative projects,
- 7 working group to co-build (data, research, ideal open lab, training, assessment).

PA4ALL (LL)

Context

PA4ALL is an abbreviation for Precision Agriculture for All, which is the main scope of our Living Lab, to introduce all the actors in the agriculture production chain to precision agriculture tools. The host organisation of PA4ALL is BioSense Institute, Institute for research and development of information technology in biosystems. Research and innovation at BioSense Institute is developed in a close interaction with farmers and the agri-food sector, government bodies, entrepreneurs and business community, international researchers, and citizens.

***Aim:** To create a meeting place for all relevant stakeholders and a new generation of open innovations which will be readily used, and which will bring benefits across the entire value-chain.*

Activities

- Introducing precision agriculture to high school students.
- Installing meteorology stations around Serbia to enhance the adaption of precision agriculture.
- Creating a free online service which involves precision agriculture tools.

Participants

Researchers, farmers, citizens, students, industry stakeholders, policy makers.

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

Since BIOS Institute (PA4ALL) is involved in multidisciplinary research performed in the fields of micro and nanoelectronics, communications, signal processing, remote sensing, big data, robotics and biosystems we include academia and highly skilled professionals to share their knowledge on the subject.

We engage policy makers and representatives of the governmental and civil society in conversation about the importance of equipping the society with precision agriculture tools and the following knowledge. We have a broad system of stakeholders in Serbia, such as teachers, professors, students, citizens, agriculture producers, SMEs, non-governmental organisations, and others who we involve in our activities and projects.

Innovative Farmers (LL)

Context

Innovative Farmers is a non-profit network that gives farmers in the UK research support and funding on their terms. This helps farmers find lasting solutions to practical problems, from managing weeds and pests with fewer chemicals to testing more sustainable animal feeds. Members of the network can connect with other innovative farmers, researchers and stakeholders who share a passion for finding new ways to farm and can take part in farmer-led trials, known as “field labs”. The programme covers all farming sectors and works with both conventional, regenerative, and organic farmers.

***Aim:** To speed up the adoption of innovative practices that increase farm sustainability, resilience and animal health and welfare as well as enhancing farmers' confidence in on-farm experimentation and fostering new collaborations.*

Activities

- Specialist advice and support to get field labs off the ground.
- Connecting farmers with other farmers and facilitating the co-design process, and with researchers for advice on trial design and time to do assessments, monitoring, and analysis.

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- Matching the group with a coordinator to keep the field lab on track and facilitating the co-design process, as well as a researcher for advice on trial design and time to do assessments, monitoring, and analysis.
- Organising network events, conference sessions and other field lab open days.
- Communication: open days, webinars, monthly e-newsletters, knowledge exchange videos and blogs, social media, open-source publishing of progress and findings, dedicated web content for each field lab, and working with the farming media to feature field labs and the farmers in the network.
- Reporting, evaluation, and quality assurance. This includes input from a steering group made up of industry experts and academics who assess field lab applications.

Soil scientists Lynda Deeks trains hemp growers on low-cost ways to assess their soil health in a field lab exploring how growing hemp impacts soil health, carbon sequestration and biodiversity.

Participants

Farmers, researchers, advisors, NGOs, industry stakeholders.

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

How to set up a field lab

1 It starts with an idea

From an existing discussion group, project or network, a group of farmers or growers come together around an idea

2 Identifying existing knowledge and a suitable topic

Supported by a coordinator, the group establishes a topic or challenge they'd like to explore and sets realistic expectations and outcomes for the field lab.

3 Formulating a clear research question and co-designing a trial

Innovative Farmers matches the group with a researcher so they can develop a practical research question to be answered through a field lab. The group works collaboratively to design what data to record and monitor, ensuring the trial is both scientifically robust and practical for a working farm. The plan should be realistic about the roles, responsibilities, and time that the trialists and researchers can commit

4 Applying for funding

The group can apply to the Innovative Farmers Research Fund to cover trial costs.

5 Progressing the field lab

The group meets regularly and uses social media to discuss insights and tips and make sure the trial stays on track and data is collected regularly.

6 Analyse results

The group jointly analyses the findings and identifies what they have discovered over the duration of the field lab.

7 Share findings

The results and tips are shared with the farming community through events, online and in the media so everyone can benefit.

8 Next steps

The farmers apply what they have learned to their farming business and explore whether a new field lab or other funding streams are needed to answer further questions.

Achievements

- Launched over 120 field labs across the UK.
- Over 600 farmers have taken part in on-farm trials through the field labs.
- Half of farmers have made changes to their farming practices because of field labs.
- Real changes on the ground include:
 - 50% of UK hops growers now grow cover crops in their hop yards.
 - Identifying innovative solutions which increase farm sustainability and reduce costs.
 - Supporting large, long-term, participatory trials, looking at silvopasture.
 - Changes on individual farms, e.g., growing buckwheat as a permanent part of a rotation for couch grass control.

- Farmers and researchers equipped with research evidence to make the case for further government support for agroecological practices.
- Farmers and researchers demonstrating the value of collaboration and on-farm trials, enabling them to access larger external funding pots to continue with their research.
- 84% of people in the network have learned something new.
- 12,000 farmers have engaged in another activity such as attending on-farm events, conferences, watching our knowledge exchange videos or reading the Innovative Farmers newsletter.
- Showcasing the network: Farming press coverage of field lab activity and farmer voices is read over 133,000 times a month.

CARBONFARM (LL)

Context

Carbonfarm is a cooperation between the Danish agricultural universities at Aarhus and Copenhagen, The Danish Innovation Centre for Organic farming, Danish low-till farmer association (FRDK), four skilled and innovative farmers and the Danish Agro-industry. Carbonfarm combines research and a practical approach to develop and demonstrate sustainable agricultural systems for the future.

***Aim:** By bringing together the researchers, advisors, and innovative farmers the aim of Carbonfarm is to develop, document and implement sustainable farming systems based on conservation agriculture principals in both organic and conventional farming.*

Participants

Researchers, NGOs, farmers, and advisors.

Activities

- Research in agronomic, climate and environmental effects of conservation agricultural (CA) systems: (soil structure, weeds, yields and quality, nitrous oxide emissions; nutrient assimilation - and leaching, etc).
- Measure and document effects of CA systems on biodiversity (bees, beetles, earthworms, soil surface predators, antipodes (collembola), arbuscular mycorrhiza, etc).
- Research effects and mechanisms of CA for building up the soil carbon content (measuring and modelling carbon content in soils).
- Develop and implement a sustainable system with Conservation Agriculture elements suitable for Danish conventional and organic farming systems.
- Develop mechanical solutions for Danish CA primarily in organic trials.
- Demonstration and dissemination of project results to farmers, researchers and advisory services (field days, seminars, webinars, visit from local and international farmers/experts, manuals, videos and articles etc.).

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

The Carbonfarm living lab is based on established large scale field trials at four Danish farms. Two conventional and two organic farms are involved. The treatments are a reference of a traditional plough system, a low tillage system without ploughing, and two conservation agricultural systems with low- or no till systems. Field Plots are 20 – 24 x 50 meters and the trials are run by/with farmers using their own machinery – with a few exceptions.

Living lab field trials:

- Treatment 1: Reference (Normal tillage intensity with ploughing). Limited use of catch crops.
- Treatment 2: "Low tillage". Without ploughing mainly cultivation by harrowing and use of catch crops.
- Treatment 3: CA "Minimal tillage, " leaving plant residues and optimal use of catch crop in mixtures.
- Treatment 4: CA "Carbon optimising", with minimal tillage.

Achievements

- CA is also a robust and sustainable cultivation system under Danish conditions.
- The non-organic experimental fields show that CA can be implemented, and yields can be obtained similar to traditional cultivation systems with tillage.
- There is great interest among conventional farmers to operate their plant-breeding in whole or in part according to CA principles.
- Weed control is a major challenge when plowing and tillage are reduced in organic crops.
- CA has a significant potential to increase biodiversity both above and below ground in Danish fields, although the positive effects on aphid predators only affected the spiders.

InoFA – Internet of Food Alliance Support Office (LL)

Context

InoFA was created as a project in 2020 with funding by the Greek General Secretariat for Research and Innovation. It designed 11 internal projects, to the total value of 350.000€, engaging a total of 30 of its members, now in the early stages of the implementation phase. In addition, the facilitator organisation was granted 200.000€ for support and coordination activities. Adopting a proactive approach, and with a view to the post-project economic sustainability of the network, the InoFA Support Office was established in July 2022 as a legal entity with its own Registry and BIC numbers.

Principles & Values

ALL-Ready - The European Agroecology Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: preparation phase

D3.2 Reports of ALL-Ready Pilot Co-Creation Experiences – Report n.3 – 01 December 2023

InoFA is a vertically integrated, quadruple helix, cluster dedicated to the digitalisation of a sustainable Greek agrifood sector. With over 80 members, InoFA covers the whole of Greece.

***Aim:** Create a permanent network of real economy players along the supply chain, technology and service providers, RTOs and civil society institutions, with a view to promoting the sustainability of the agrifood sector.*

Participants

Researchers, farmers, tech provider

Activities

Given the green deal EU policy, and in order to stay relevant to the needs of the real economy members, it was decided that InoFA should design projects and provide them with tools that minimise the environmental footprint of their activities.

Thus, we engaged them with:

- Bio stimulants as an alternative to chemical fertilisers,
- compostable cover ground covers,
- Utilisation of photonic technologies for yield and quality management,
- Sustainable irrigation,
- Sustainable management of free-range bovines, and other innovative practices, as means of surviving the transition period.

At the same time, we make farmers visible by facilitating:

- short supply chains,
- digital traceability and proof of provenance and digital marketing.

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

Producer-driven innovation is at the heart of InoFA. The issues to be dealt with are identified by the real economy players and their common characteristic is that they have an immediate impact on their economic sustainability. From this starting point, experimenting, piloting and demonstrating in real commercial settings is imperative for the credibility of the proposed solution; this often complicates things, but it is unavoidable.

From our experience, the success of innovation facilitation requires the combination (a) of constant, mundane, engagement with intermittent innovation interventions (b) knowledge transfer with experience exchange with a view to creating a community of practice. These underlying principles dictate more or less the means by which we involve users in the innovation process.

The communication with real economy players is both direct and mediated, through for instance local field agronomists who are their everyday service providers. Communication with such intermediaries is both personal, informal and through occasional organised meetings, both local and interregional. The same applies to communication with farmers;

special attention is given in this context to encouraging peer-to-peer exchanges among farmers from different regions.

While projects are developing, progress is discussed, and results disseminated through focus groups and workshops.

Achievements

- By regulating irrigation through InoFA installed soil moisture sensors and electronic valves olive and bean cultivators in Western and Central Macedonia have made saving not only on their water usage by 25% but also on fungicides. Irrigation management applications have been developed by InoFA RTOs.
- By using microbial biostimulants in table grape vineyards, in conjunction with digital soil analysis software developed by InoFA RTOs, we have reduced the use of fertilisers by 25%, making savings in the region of 250€ per hectare. In addition, at least one composting facility start up is in the process of being established, thereby producing an import substitution effect (currently most commercial biostimulants are imported from Spain and Serbia).
- By creating interactive maps of the presence of Mediterranean fruit flies in Peloponnese, we alert local farmers on the likelihood of danger for their olive trees; it is hard to assign a financial figure to the impact of this service.
- By using light sensors in the greenhouses in Crete, members are improving their yields and making savings in the replacement of the aging plastic sheets. In addition, the cooperative agronomist is able to provide benchmarked advice to their members regarding their cultivation practices.
- By proactively training InoFA members to measuring their CO2 impact using the "Cool Farm Alliance" tool, we have given them access as suppliers to A.B. Vassilopoulos, the 3rd largest chain in Greece.
- By establishing a digitally supported short supply chain for meat from indigenous bovine breeds in Central and Eastern Macedonia, we have increased the revenues of local farmers by about 0,50€ per kilo, or on average, by 150€ per animal.

Living Lab LIT OUESTEREL - Territorial Innovation Living Lab 'Livestock Territories of Western France (LL)

Context

It was one of the 24 winners of the project call of the "Territoires d'Innovation" (Innovation Territories) launched by the French government (mid 2019), with the project officially starting in January 2020 after more than three years of preparation and construction. The Living Lab was implemented through an Association ("Association LIT OUESTEREL) created in January 2020.

- Around 40 partners at the creation.
- More than 60 partners today.

Living Lab is funded by the "Banque des Territoires", and the three Regional Councils of Bretagne, Normandie, and the Pays de la Loire, plus membership fees of the Association.

Principles & Values

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ALL-Ready - The European Agroecology Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: preparation phase

D3.2 Reports of ALL-Ready Pilot Co-Creation Experiences – Report n.3 – 01 December 2023

The Living Lab LIT OUESTEREL is localised in the West part of France (Regions of Bretagne, Normandie, and Pays de la Loire) where livestock production is particularly important (for ex., around 75% of the French production of pigs). It includes three infra-regional pilot territories. It covers the three species of poultry, pork, and cattle milk and meat at the three stages of livestock, transport and slaughtering. It is focused on animal welfare and health in the framework of the One Health / One Welfare concept.

Aim: *The Living Lab LIT OUESTEREL aims at reconciling livestock and society by co-constructing projects focused on the improvement of animal welfare, the reduction in the use of veterinary products in livestock (notably antimicrobials), and the improvement of working, living and income of the different actors of the livestock chains, notably livestock producers.*

Participants

Farmers, livestock producers, citizens, consumers, livestock professional actors

Activities

- Co-construction of animal welfare labels.
- Development of projects aimed at identifying and reconciling livestock and society.
- Co-construction of solutions with stakeholders.
- Co-construction of Research-Development-Innovation (RDI) projects.
- Hunt for innovations (bottom-up innovations implemented by livestock producers and top down innovations conceived).
- Construction of formations (notably “e-formations”) on animal welfare and health.
- Communication activities towards all stakeholders.

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

Methods and tools vary in function of the project considered. A common characteristic of the different projects is the co-design of each project by the different types of stakeholders in line with the functioning principle of Living Labs.

Achievements

Sharing knowledge and connecting people

- More than 60 stakeholders involved in the Living Lab
- Two animal welfare labels (for broiler and pork)
- Development on an original method (the method of the "Y") aimed at facilitating the dialogue between the different types of stakeholders and in their involvement in co-construction projects.
- Implementation of more than 40 RDI projects: alternatives to the raw castration of piglets; multi-criteria assessment of innovative pig buildings; co-construction of innovative pig buildings targeting different market segments; just commitment of livestock producers in animal welfare approaches; how to speak of animal welfare with the citizens and the consumers, how to speak of animal welfare with livestock professional actors; consumption of animal products (meat) over the next decade; etc.
- Identification and characterisation of more than 200 bottom up and top-down innovations focused on animal welfare and health, just commitment of livestock producers in
- Communication activities towards all stakeholders

PFN Hessen – Praxisforschungsnetzwerk

für den Ökologischen Land- und Gemüsebau (LL)

Context

The development and establishment of the PFN Hessen is part of the Organic Action Plan Hessen 2020-2025 and is funded by the Hessian Ministry of the Environment (HMuKLV). The Association of Organic Farming in Hessen (VÖL) e.V. is the network's project management organisation and has been coordinating the establishment of the network since 2021.

Principles & Values

In this network, people from practice, extension, and research work as partners at eye level. Together we work on questions and topics from the practice of organic agriculture and develop research projects with and for the practice.

***Aim:** Our aim is to develop and establish practical innovations through joint research projects that will further develop organic farming for the future.*

Participants

Researchers, farmers, advisors, network coordinators

Activities

Currently, more than 20 organic farmers, advisors from organic farming associations, the State Office of Agriculture Hesse and researchers from various Hessian research institutions

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and the network coordinators are part of PFN Hessen. At regular meetings we exchange ideas, discuss, and learn from and with each other to work together as equals in a dynamic network structure. Experts from practice, extension, and research work together in three project groups (pig, arable and vegetable farming) in a participatory process and develop projects and implement them together. More groups will follow.

Current Projects:

- Arable farming: Influence of three tillage methods and different catch crop mixtures on humus build-up and nitrogen retention in the soil-plant system.
- Vegetable Farming: Effect of compost or manure in combination with catch crops on soil water holding capacity and humus build-up.

Cooperation:

- The "Netzwerke Ökokompost Hessen" (NÖK) is a four-year start-up project of the Organic Action Plan Hessen 2020-2025. It serves the sustainable networking of stakeholders for the production and application of quality-assured biowaste and green waste composts in organic agriculture at all levels.

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

A good organisational structure of the 5 groups of actors is of great importance for the successful establishment of the practice research network: VÖL coordinates the participatory cooperation of farmers, extension and research (represented by the universities) in coordination with the funders. Regular project group work and professional exchange of all network members and external experts as well as regular feedback and knowledge loops and evaluations are important components of this co-creative network.

ROADMAP (LL-like project)

Context

ROADMAP is a 4-year EU-funded project that will foster transitions towards prudent antimicrobial use (AMU) in animal production in a large variety of contexts, by favouring a rethinking of antimicrobial decision-systems all along the food supply chain.

***Aim:** foster transitions towards prudent use of antimicrobials (AMs) in animal production in different contexts to manage antimicrobial resistance (AMR).*

Reduced antimicrobial use (AMU) will be achieved by enhancing antimicrobial decision-systems along the food and drug supply chains. ROADMAP will focus on supporting animal health and welfare through prevention and health promotion actions.

Participants

National public bodies/authorities, local public bodies and municipalities, researchers/research institutes, universities, advisors, farmers, retailers, SMEs, large companies, and consumers/consumer organisations.

Activities

- analyse the socio-economic drivers of AMU,
- engage with animal health professionals, stakeholders, and policy makers.
- develop tailored strategies for change and propose transition scenarios in diverse farm animal production systems in Europe and low- and middle-income countries.

Organic Research, Development, and Demonstration Program (Funding scheme)

Context

ICROFS, International Centre for Research in Organic Food Systems, founded in 1996, hosts the Organic RDD program with projects supporting the Danish organic farming and food systems, funded by the Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries. Organic RDD is providing funds for LLs and RIs. Supported projects must include a research part and the results be focused on the end-user through multi-actor approach organised LL.

Principles & Values

ICROFS is contributing to the development of sustainable food systems based on the organic philosophy and the organic principles. It contributes with new knowledge, which supports reliability, innovation and development of organic farming and food systems.

***Aim:** The development of a market-driven and competitive organic sector and the support of continuous growth in the Danish organic sector.*

Participants

Funders, ministry, researcher, farmers, NGOs, and industry stakeholders.

Activities

- Coordinating the Organic RDD program

- Coordinating the European ERA-NET Core Organic
- Participate as partners in research projects: communication, dissemination, and knowledge synthesis. Project management
- Runs the open access archive Organic Eprints (including Germany and Switzerland)
- Produces knowledge synthesis about organic farming

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

The Organic RDD program focuses on actor driven research by use of multi-actor approach organic LL.

The funded projects must include end-users and must include actors from the whole value chain from the planning phase.

Achievements

- ICROFS has coordinated Danish Organic research calls since 1996.
- ICROFS has coordinated the ERA-NET Core Organic since 2004 and has coordinated 6 transnational calls.
- Produces knowledge synthesis about organic farming.

Appendix 2: Meeting agendas

1st pilot network meeting

DAY 1

13 December Time	Activity	Presenters, Facilitators
9:55 -10:00	Waiting for everyone to join via zoom	
10:00 – 10:30	Introductory round (ice-breakers)	All
10:30 – 10:45	Introduction to the meeting's objectives, facilitators and to the Pilot Network	Korinna Varga, ÖMKI
10:45 – 10:55	ALL-READY project	Heather INRAE McKhann,
10:55 – 11:15	European Agroecology Partnership	Benjamin SCAR-AE Sanchez,
11:15 – 11:20	Break	
11:20 - 12:20	ALL-READY: Mission and Vision of the future European Agroecology Network	Muriel Mambrini, Bastian Goldel, INRAE
12:20 – 13:20	Lunch break	

13:20 – 14:20	Pilot member (LLs/RIs) introduction PART 1 1. LLAEBIO (Living Lab on Agro-Ecology and Organic Farming in Flanders) 2. PA4ALL 3. Long term experiment on organic and conventional arable cropping systems (CROPSYS) 4. Carbon Farm 5. Occitanum 6. OasYs	Pilot members
14:20 – 14:30	Yoga Break	
14:30 – 15:30	Pilot member (LLs/RIs) introduction PART 2 7. ÖMKi On-Farm Living Lab 8. Innovative Farmers 9. ROADMAP 10. LifeWatch ERIC 11. LTSER Zone Atelier Plaine & Val de Sèvre 12. ReWet_DK	Pilot members
15:30 – 15:40	Yoga Break	
15:40 – 16:30	Pilot member (LLs/RIs) introduction PART 3 13. Agricultural Climate Solutions 14. Organic Research Development and Demonstration Program 15. Institute for Sustainable Food 16. BIOBASE (CBIO) 17. Guadalinfo Living Lab	
16:30– 17:00	Pilot network expectations exercise	Korinna Varga, Judit Fehér, ÖMKi
17:00– 17:10	Conclusion, End of 1st Day	Korinna Varga, ÖMKi
17:10-17:45	Grab a drink and imagine the future of your LL/RI (Virtual Networking)	Everyone

DAY 2

14 December Time	Activity	Presenters, Facilitators
9:25 – 9:30	Waiting for everyone to join via zoom	
9:30 – 10:20	<u>Engaging with the WPs</u> WP presentations, timeline of related activities Discussion round with the participants	WP Leads
10:20 – 12:00	Co-creation of joint activities for the pilot network (workshop)	Korinna Varga, Judit Fehér, ÖMKi

12:00 13:00	-	Lunch break	
13:00 15:00	-	Exploring the added value of a future network and competencies for transition to agroecology and to run LL/RI (workshop)	Gerald Schwartz (TI), Isidora Stojacic (Biosense), Jo Bijttebier (ILVO), Sylvie Fosselle (ILVO), Marion Liberloo (ILVO) Koen Vervoort (ENoLL)
15:00 15:10	-	Break	
15:10 16:50	-	Building a Virtual Lab that suits the pilot network members' needs (workshop)	José Manuel Avila, Juan Miguel Gonzalez Aranda, Life Watch ERIC
16:50 – 17:10		Conclusion & next steps End of the 1st pilot meeting	Korinna Varga, ÖMKi

2nd pilot network meeting

4 July Time	Activity	Presenters, Facilitators	Questions to think about in advance
11:00 - 11:30	Arrival to VAC Building		
11:30 - 13:00	Lunch	All	
13:00 - 13:20	Welcome and introduction to the pilot network workshop	Korinna Varga (ÖMKi)	
13:20 - 15:30	Operationalizing the collaborative themes: Thematic working group discussions	All	1.What are your expectations of the Thematic Working Groups? 2.What do you think what is feasible to do in the working groups by the end of the project? (by September 2023)
15:30 - 16:00	BREAK		
16:00 - 17:30	Learning roundtable: Best practices for co-creation and involving stakeholders	Rebecca Swinn (Innovative Farmers), Chris McPhee (AAFC), All	Think about an issue or challenge that your LL/RI is facing in relation to co-creation or involving stakeholders
17:30 - 17:45	Conclusions End of Day 1	All	
17:45 - 18:00	BREAK		

18:00 – 22:00	Boat tour & Guided culinary walk	All	
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5 July Time	Activity	Presenters, Facilitators
8:00 – 8:30	Arrival to VAC Building	
8:30– 8:40	Introduction to Day 2	Korinna Varga (ÖMKi)
8:40 – 9:10	Why is a European Network important? Needs, challenges, and benefits of a future European network	Gerald Schwarz (Thünen Institute), Isidora Stojacic (Biosense)
9:10 – 9:40	What competencies and skills can a European Network improve? Prototyping the capacity building program	Jo Bijtzebier (ILVO), Koen Vervoort (ENOLL)
9:40 – 10:40	How can a virtual environment support a European Network? Functionalities of the Virtual Lab	José Manuel Avila, Iria Soto (Lifewatch)
10:40 – 10:50	BREAK	
10:50 – 11:10	Conclusions End of Day 2	All
11:10 – 12:15	Travel by train to DEMO Day	All
12:15 – 13:00	Lunch in Hansbeke	All
13:00 – 17:00	DEMO DAY	All

3rd pilot network meeting

21 Nov Time	Activity	Presenters, Facilitators
11:00 – 11:30	Arrival to CEU Building	
11:30 – 13:00	LUNCH	All
13:00 – 13:10	Welcome and introduction to the 3rd pilot network meeting	Korinna Varga (ÖMKi)

13:10 – 13:35	Ice-breaker: Five fingers	All
13:35 – 13:55	Introduction to the ALL-Ready project and to European Agroecology Partnership	Heather McKhann (INRAE)
13:55 – 15:20	Achievements of ALL-Ready <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Framework for agroecology transition and vision and mission of the future network 2. Mapping agroecological LL/RIs in Europe 3. Pilot network 4. Co-developing an implementation plan for the future network 5. Capacity building programme 6. Virtual Lab for agroecological LL/RIs 7. ALL-Ready Communications + Q&A	Muriel Mambrini (INRAE), Torsten Rodel (Aarhus), Korinna Varga (ÖMKi), Gerald Schwarz (Thünen), Isabelle Couture (ENoLL), José Manuel Avila (Lifewatch ERIC), Miguel de Porrás (Fibl Europe)
15:20 – 15:50	BREAK	
15:50 – 18:00	Pilot member interviews	Pilot members
18:00 – 18:10	BREAK	
18:10 – 18:45	Walking to Tasting Table – Wine Cellar, Budapest	All
18:45 – 20:15	Hungarian Wine Tasting coupled with typical cheese and charcuterie tasting Tasting Table – Wine Cellar, Bródy Sándor utca 9.	All
20:30 – 22:00	Dinner at Vígvarjú restaurant Vigadó tér 2	All

22 Nov	Activity	Presenters, Facilitators
7:30 – 8:00	Arrival to CEU Building	
8:00 – 8:10	Introduction to Day 2	Korinna Varga (ÖMKi)
8:10 – 9:10	Pilot network activity update and discussion	Korinna Varga (ÖMKi) + pilot members
9:10 – 9:30	BREAK	

9:30 - 12:10	Learning Roundtable session: Co-creation tools to address the gap between the needs of scientists and farmers	Ana Allamand (Soil Association), Chris McPhee (AAFC), Korinna Varga (ÖMKi) + Pilot members
12:10 - 13:30	LUNCH	
13:30 - 15:30	Exploring the governance of the future European Network	Gerald Schwarz (Thünen), Isidora Stojacic (Biosense) + pilot members
15:30 - 16:00	BREAK	All
16:00 - 18:00	Co-designing the capacity building training items	Isabelle Couture (EnoLL), Sylvie Fosselle (ILVO) + pilot members
18:00 - 18:10	Preparing for Day 3 and intro to the social programme	Korinna Varga (ÖMKi)
18:10 - 18:45	BREAK	
18:45 - 20:30	Guided walking + boat tour	All
20:45 - 22:00	Dinner at TwentySix restaurant Budapest, Király u. 26, 1061	All

23 Nov	Activity	Presenters, Facilitators
7:45 - 8:10	Arrival to Hungarian Academy of Sciences building, parking lot (3 min from CEU) Address: Széchenyi István tér 9.	
8:15 - 9:15	Bus to Szár	All
9:15 - 12:30	Field visit at Csoroszllya Farm	Ágoston Nobillis (Csoroszllya Farm) + All
12:30 - 13:30	LUNCH	
13:30 - 14:30	Travel back to Budapest (reflections about the field visit on the way back)	All
14:30 - 16:30	Discussing the Agroecology Virtual Lab - testing version	José Manuel Avila, Iria Soto (Lifewatch ERIC) + pilot members
16:30 - 17:00	Next steps and wrap-up	Korinna Varga (ÖMKi)
17:00 -	End of meeting	

4th pilot network meeting

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ALL-Ready - The European Agroecology Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: preparation phase

D3.2 Reports of ALL-Ready Pilot Co-Creation Experiences – Report n.3 – 01 December 2023

14 June Time	Activity	Presenters, Facilitators
8:30 - 9:00	Arrival to SupAgro	
9:00 – 9:10	Welcome and introduction to the 4th pilot network meeting	Korinna Varga (ÖMKi)
9:10 – 9:40	Ice-breaker	All
9:40 – 10:30	Looking back & ahead: Pilot network achievements, progress and the future + Discussion	Korinna Varga (ÖMKi)
10:30 – 12:00	Joint reflection on pilot co-creation activities	Korinna Varga (ÖMKi), Valéria Csonka (ÖMKi), May Hobeika (Ecologic) + pilot members
12:00-13:00	LUNCH	
13:00 – 14:40	Capacity building training: Systems Thinking part 1	Jo Bijttebier (ILVO), Sylvie Fosselle (ILVO) + pilot members
14:40-14:50	BREAK	
14:50 – 16:00	Capacity building training: Systems Thinking part 2	Jo Bijttebier (ILVO), Sylvie Fosselle (ILVO), Isabelle Couture (ENoLL) + pilot members
16:00 – 18:00	Developing an implementation plan for the European Network	Gerald Schwarz (Thünen) + pilot members
18:00 – 18:20	BREAK	
18:30 – 20:30	Guided tour in the historical centre of Montpellier	All
20:30 – 21:30	Dinner at La Chistera restaurant	All

15 June Time	Activity	Presenters, Facilitators
8:30 – 9:00	Arrival to SupAgro	
9:00 – 10:30	Capacity building training: Living Lab Model, Real-life Experimentation & Facilitation Techniques part 1	Dimitri Schuurman (IMEC) Gilles Wuyts, (IMEC) + pilot members
10:30 – 10:40	BREAK	

10:40 – 12:00	Capacity building training: Living Lab Model, Real-life Experimentation & Facilitation Techniques part 2	Dimitri Schuurman (IMEC) Gilles Wuyts, (IMEC) + pilot members + pilot members
12:00 – 13:00	LUNCH	
13:00 – 14:00	Travel to Mas Numérique (Open Lab VITI)	
14:00 – 15:30	Field visit: Getting to know Occitanum Living Lab & How to co-create services with farmer and firms	Jacques-Eric Bergez, Laurent Gourdon, Ines Maranon (Occitanum), Bruno Tisseyre (AgroTIC Sup Agro)
15:30 – 16:00	BREAK	All
16:00 – 17:00	Field visit: Mas Numérique digital farm tour	Romain Girardot (AgroTIC Sup Agro)
17:00 – 18:00	Field visit: Discovering the Mobilab	Basile Ploteau, (AgroTIC Sup Agro)
18:00 – 18:20	BREAK	
18:20 – 19:30	Freetime at the Mediterrean sea	All
19:30 – 20:30	Dinner at Albatros restaurant	All
20:30 – 21:30	Travel Back to Montpellier	All

16 June Time	Activity	Presenters, Facilitators
8:30 – 9:00	Arrival to SupAgro	
9:00 – 9:30	Starting the 3rd day	All
9:30 – 10:30	Finalizing the Agroecology Virtual Lab and discussing innovation, data and IPR management	José Manuel Avila (LifeWatch), Iria Soto (LifeWatch) + pilot members
10:30 – 10:50	BREAK	
10:50 – 11:40	Next steps for the pilot network	Korinna Varga (ÖMKi) + pilot members

11:40 – 12:00	Feedback round & wrap-up	Korinna Varga (ÖMKi) + pilot members
12:00 – 13:00	LUNCH	
13:00 -	End of meeting	

Appendix 3: List of participants

1st pilot network meeting

Nr	Name	Organisation/affiliation	Type of stakeholder
1	Anton Rasmussen	CarbonFarm	LL coordinator/Organic advisor
2	Bastian Goldel	INRAE	WP1 Lead/Note-taker
3	Benjamin Sanchez	SCAR-AE	Presenter
4	Chiara de Notaris	CROPSYS	RI coordinator/Researcher
5	Chris McPhee	AAFC	LL coordinator/ Innovation management specialist
6	Gerald Schwartz	TI	WP4 Lead/Expert
7	Gerardo Romero	Guadalinfo	LL coordinator/Network coordinator
8	Heather McKhann	INRAE	Project Coordinator
9	Holly Croft	Institute for Sustainable Food	RI coordinator/Researcher
10	Isidora Stojacic	PA4ALL	LL coordinator/WP4 expert
11	Ivana Trkulja	Organic RDD	Scientific officer
12	Jacques-Eric Bergez	Occitanum	LL coordinator/ Researcher
13	Jo Bijttebier	ILVO	WP5 facilitator
14	Jose Manuel Avila	LifeWatch-ERIC	RI coordinator/WP6 Lead/Facilitator
15	Juan Miguel Gonzalez Aranda	LifeWatch ERIC	WP6 Lead/Facilitator
16	Judit Fehér	ÖMKi	WP3 Lead/Facilitator
17	Kiril Manevski	CBIO	RI coordinator/Researcher
18	Koen Vervoort	ENoLL	WP5 Lead/Note-taker
19	Korinna Varga	ÖMKi On-farm Living Lab/ÖMKi	LL coordinator/WP3 Lead/Facilitator
20	Lieve de Cock	LLAEBIO	LL coordinator /Researcher
21	Malene Jakobsen	Organic RDD	RI coordinator/Scientific officer
22	Merete Studnitz	ROADMAP	LL coordinator/ Scientific officer
23	Muriel Mambrini	INRAE	WP1 Lead/Facilitator

24	Ophélie Bonnet	INRAE	Project Manager
25	Paola Eulalio	DG Agri	Policy maker
26	Rebecca Swinn	Innovative Farmers	LL coordinator/Network coordinator
27	Rocio Mantero Cejudo	LifeWatch ERIC	WP6 Facilitation
28	Sabrina Gaba	ZAPVS	RI coordinator/Researcher
29	Sandra Novak	OasYs	RI coordinator/Researcher
30	Susana Gaona-Saez	DG Agri	Policy maker
31	Sylvie Fosselle	ILVO	WP5 facilitator
32	Torsten Berg	REWET	LL coordinator/ Researcher
33	Vincent Bretagnolle	ZAPVS	Researcher

2nd pilot network meeting

Nr	Name	Organisation/affiliation	Type of stakeholder
1	Cécile Bruere	Occitanum	Pilot member
2	Lieve de Cock	LLAEBIO	Pilot member
3	Kiril Manevski	Biobase	Pilot member
4	Anton Rasmussen	CarbonFarm	Pilot member
5	Iria Soto Embodas	LifeWatch ERIC	Pilot member
6	Isidora Stojacic	PA4ALL/Biosense	Pilot member/ WP4 deputy lead
7	Rebecca Swinn	Innovative Farmers	Pilot member
8	Chris McPhee	AAFC	Pilot member
9	Ivana Trkulja	ROADMAP/Organic RDD	Pilot member
10	Holly Croft	ISF	Pilot member
11	Korinna Varga	ÖMKi On-farm LL/ÖMKi	Pilot member/WP3 Lead
12	José Manuel Avila	LifeWatch ERIC	WP6 Lead
13	Jo Bijttebier	ILVO	WP5 Deputy lead
14	Miguel de Porrás	FiBL Europe	WP7 Lead
15	Bastian Goldel	INRAE	WP1 team member
16	Muriel Mambrini Doudet	INRAE	WP1 Lead
17	Heather McKhann	INRAE	Project coordinator
18	May Hobeika	Ecologic	WP3 team member
19	Rocio Perez Cano	FiBL Europe	WP7 team member
20	Gerald Schwarz	Thünen Institute	WP4 Lead
21	Koen Vervoort	ENoLL	WP5 Lead

3rd pilot network meeting

Nr	Name	Organisation/affiliation	Type of stakeholder
1	Lieve de Cock	LLAEBIO	Pilot member
2	Kiril Manevski	Biobase	Pilot member
3	Anton Rasmussen	CarbonFarm	Pilot member
4	Iria Soto Embodas	LifeWatch ERIC	Pilot member
5	Isidora Stojacic	PA4ALL/Biosense	Pilot member/ WP4 deputy lead
6	Rebecca Swinn	Innovative Farmers	Pilot member
7	Chris McPhee	AAFC	Pilot member
8	Esther Mieves	Hessen Practice Network	Pilot member
9	Philip Papadopoulos	InoFA	Pilot members
10	Maike Krauss	FiBL On-farm LL	Pilot member
11	Merete Studnitz	Roadmap	Pilot member
12	Korinna Varga	ÖMKi On-farm LL/ÖMKi	Pilot member/WP3 Lead
13	José Manuel Avila	LifeWatch ERIC	WP6 Lead
14	Bastian Goldel	INRAE	WP1 team member
15	Muriel Mambrini Doudet	INRAE	WP1 Lead
16	Heather McKhann	INRAE	Project coordinator
17	May Hobeika	Ecologic	WP3 team member
18	Valéria Csonka	ÖMKi	WP3 team member
19	Gerald Schwarz	Thünen Institute	WP4 Lead
20	Isabelle Couture	ENoLL	WP5 Lead
21	Sylvie Fosselle	ILVO	WP3/5 team member
22	Miguel de Porras	FiBL Europe	WP7 Lead

Nr	Name	Organisation/affiliation	Type of stakeholder
1	Lieve de Cock	LLAEBIO	Pilot member
2	Anton Rasmussen	CarbonFarm	Pilot member
3	Iria Soto Embodas	LifeWatch ERIC	Pilot member
4	Rebecca Swinn	Innovative Farmers	Pilot member
5	Chris McPhee	AAFC	Pilot member
6	Charalampos Kotzamanidis	InoFA	Pilot member
7	Maike Krauss	FIBL On-farm LL	Pilot member
8	Merete Studnitz	Roadmap	Pilot member
9	Korinna Varga	ÖMKi On-farm LL/ÖMKi	Pilot member/WP3 Lead
10	José Manuel Avila	LifeWatch ERIC	WP6 Lead
11	Bastian Goldel	INRAE	WP1 team member
12	Muriel Mambrini Doudet	INRAE	WP1 Lead
13	May Hobeika	Ecologic	WP3 team member
14	Valéria Csonka	ÖMKi	WP3 team member
15	Gerald Schwarz	Thünen Institute	WP4 Lead
16	Isabelle Couture	ENoLL	WP5 Lead
17	Sylvie Fosselle	ILVO	WP3/5 team member
18	Jo Bijttebier	ILVO	WP3/5 team member
19	Antonia Riedel	Ecologic	WP3 team member
20	Gerardo Romero	Guadalinfo	Pilot member
21	Jacques Eric Bergez	Occitanum	Pilot member
22	Ines Maranon	Occitanum	Pilot member

23	Sven Fahrner	EMPHASIS	Pilot member
24	Dolinda Cavallo	ENoLL	WP5 Lead

4th pilot network meeting

Appendix 4: Individual challenges of members

Affected Member	Individual Challenges
Occitanum (LL)	Develop full innovative digital tools assessment (LCA, SLCA, EA)
	Deal with the differences in the different Open Labs
LLAEBIO (LL)	Tightening the link between organic and conventional sector
	Setting up (and fund) new research activities
Innovative Farmers (LL)	Getting 5 agricultural colleges to include farmer-led research/on-farm trials as part of modules
	Continuation of some field labs (facilitation, research requirements of farmers)
	Structuring better the LL - e.g., value of steering group, delivery to partners
CROPSYS (RI)	Keeping long-term coherence while addressing new needs
CarbonFarm (LL)	Implementing conservation agricultural practices in organic farming
Organic RDD	How to coordinate with other research programmes of similar kind
PA4ALL (LL)	How to keep confidentiality, but at the same time, disseminate LL outcomes
LifeWatch (RI)	Designing tools for LLs and RIs and the collection of enough data to validate and test them

Appendix 5. Five main collaborative themes of the pilot members linked to common challenges

Appendix 6: Five collaborative themes detailing specific activities with potential collaborators

Collaborative Theme 1	Specific Activity	Potential Collaborators
Collaborative research to test specific agroecological practices with farmers through field trials/experiments (comparable between different contexts)	Test, document and improve the agronomic, climate and environmental effects of conservation agriculture	Occitanum, IF, ISF, ÖMKi, CROPSYS, Carbonfarm, ZAPVS, AAFC, LLAEBIO, LifeWatch
	Test new digital solutions to help the transition to agroecology, e.g., remote sensing for plant protection, reducing tomato crop losses with plant sensors	Occitanum, LifeWatch, PA4ALL, Guadalinfo, ISF, ÖMKi, AAFC, Carbonfarm, Cropsys, IF
	Carbon sequestration, GHG emission, improving soil (cover crops, hemp cultivation) and water conservation to mitigate climate change (e.g., trials on no-till, reduced-till with living mulches)	ISF, ZAPVS, Carbonfarm, LLAEBIO, AAFC, IF, LifeWatch, ÖMKi, OasYs
	Diversification (crop, production, rotational) on multiple level e.g., intercropping exploring good combinations and yields, soybean variety tests for crop rotation	OASYS, CROPSYS, ZAPVS, ISF, IF, ÖMKi, Carbonfarm, LLAEBIO, AAFC
	Organic nutrient replenishment	ÖMKi, IF, AAFC, CROPSYS
	Improving the targeting of mastitis treatments to reduce antibiotic use, improve animal welfare, develop decision system	ROADMAP, IF
	Silvopasture (integrating trees with livestock) impact on livestock health, soils, and biodiversity	IF, OASYS
	Drought resilient forage	IF, OASYS
	Testing the role of biodiversity in biocontrol,	Carbonfarm, ZAPVS, ISF

	pollination, organic matter recycling	
Cross-cutting activities:	Conducting fixed (yield, nitrate leaching, weed pressure, nutrients) and extra measurements on the side (biological N ₂ fixation, N ₂ O emissions, vegetation indices, better nitrogen use efficiency) in all the above topics	ISF, AAFC, CROPSYS, ÖMKi
	Multi-criteria assessment at the farm level and valorisation of different dimensions (crop rotation, cow lifetime) in the above topics	LifeWatch, OASYS, Occitanum
	Scientific data analysis, management, and storage in the above topics	ROADMAP, CROPSYS, LifeWatch, ÖMKi (only in analysis)

Collaboration Theme 2	Specific Activity	Potential Collaborators
Collaboration for knowledge exchange and information sharing	Communication, promotion of members' agroecology-related research, project results and knowledge e.g., via website, learning networks, social media, webinar series	Organic RDD, CarbonFarm, IF, ÖMKi, AAFC, LifeWatch, CROPSYS, LLAEBIO, PA4ALL, ROADMAP, ZAPVS
	Knowledge-sharing on AE and specifically on LL approach	ÖMKi, AAFC, ROADMAP, LifeWatch, RDD, Occitanum
	Capacity-building/training/awareness on LL methods, on how to involve non-academic actors as partners for innovation (stakeholder network development)	AAFC, IF, Guadalinfo, Organic RRD, LLAEBIO, ZAPVS, Carbonfarm, PA4ALL, ÖMKi
	Determination of knowledge gaps in relation to member agroecology LLs/RIs activities and for AE transition	LLAEBIO, ROADMAP, ÖMKI
	Pilot educational model for precision agriculture solutions in agroecology, introduce tools to high school, improve digital literacy	Guadalinfo, PA4ALL, Occitanum

Collaboration Theme 3	Specific Activity	Potential Collaborators
Collaboration in long-term monitoring of agroecosystems	Monitoring of biodiversity, ecological functions, and land use	ZAPVS, LLAEBIO, CROPSYS, AAFC, ROADMAP

Collaboration Theme 4	Specific Activity	Potential Collaborators
Advice for evidence-based agricultural policy development	Policy recommendations to support knowledge-based decision making for biodiversity, agroecosystem management	ROADMAP, ZAPVS, Guadalinfo, LifeWatch, ÖMKi
	Ex-ante impact assessments	LifeWatch

Collaboration Theme 5	Specific Activity	Potential Collaborators
Facilitation of EU project proposal development	Linked to the agroecological topics mentioned in Collaborative Theme 1	LLAEBIO, Organic RDD, BIOBASE, ROADMAP

Appendix 7: 1st version of action plan

Collaborative theme	Task	Responsible members	Comment
Collaboration for knowledge exchange and information sharing among AE LLs/RIs	collaboratively map and create an inventory of (1) what is being tested right now (agroecological practices) in each LL/RI; (2) what farmers interests are in each LL/RI (3) what results/data and knowledge gaps each LL/RI has; (4) what research needs LL/RIs have; (5) what type of testing methods LL/RIs use; (6) what type of method is used for knowledge sharing and engagement of stakeholders in LL/RIs and (7) long-term monitoring data collection results of RIs Format: Joint spreadsheet created on Sharepoint shared with members. All members	ÖMKi ÖMKi creates the template spreadsheet and will send reminders to the pilot network to regularly fill out the spreadsheets (by the end of September) All members Fill in the spreadsheet	

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	fill in with their own inputs and data.		
	Collect and show existing educational curricula involving precision agri-solutions from the members	PA4ALL	
	Communication, promotion of members' agroecology-related research, project results and knowledge e.g., via website, learning networks, social media, webinar series	ÖMKi Started in January and ongoing	
	Organizing learning roundtables on specific topics with support from an other LL or RI + capture and disseminate results in the wider community	Innovative Farmers CarbonFarm ÖMKi AAFC ROADMAP Started in June and ongoing	
Facilitating networking for future research collaboration	Prepare synergies between the strategic research and innovation agenda of the AE Partnership and the needs and aims of the LL/RI network	ÖMKi	AE Partnership SRIA commenting period started in July and open until 30 September (invitation has already been sent to the members)
	Set up a small group within the network that monitors and selects relevant calls for proposal development, and (1) circulates these in the pilot network, and (2) facilitates partner matchmaking for collaboration on proposals.	Biobase ROADMAP ÖMKi LifeWatch	The initial scope of calls can potentially be expanded to calls related to topics that are not usually considered.
Advisory for evidence-based agricultural policy development	Task was not formulated during the session. Not a priority area at present.		

Appendix 8: 2nd update of the action plan

Collaborative theme	Task	Responsible members	Update
Collaboration for knowledge exchange and information sharing among AE LLs/RIs	T1. collaboratively map and create an inventory of (1) what is being tested right now (agroecological practices) in each LL/RI; (2) what farmers interests are in each LL/RI (3) what results/data and knowledge gaps each LL/RI has; (4) what research needs LL/RIs have; (5) what type of testing methods LL/RIs use; (6) what type of method is used for knowledge sharing and engagement of stakeholders in LL/RIs and (7) long-term monitoring data collection results of RIs Format: Joint spreadsheet created on Sharepoint shared with members. All members fill in with their own inputs and data.	ÖMKI ÖMKI creates the template spreadsheet and will send reminders to the pilot network to regularly fill out the spreadsheets All members Fill in the spreadsheet	Template was created, first it will be shared with WP Leads and coordination, then pilot members in January. + new items should be added to the inventory: (8) educational programmes/curriculas/experiences (EIP-AGRI projects, connection) organised by the pilot members on agroecology and (9) connections/experiences with suppliers, supermarkets (particularly on how they can be incentivised to reduce their environmental footprint by selling agroecology products)
	T2. Collect and show existing educational curricula involving precision agri-solutions from the members	PA4ALL + Small group: Innovative Farmers Biobase LLAEBIO InoFA Occitanum?	After collection in the inventory, a small group will be created to discuss the further steps

	T3. Communication, promotion of members' agroecology-related research, project results and knowledge e.g., via website, learning networks, social media, webinar series	ÖMKi (Started in January 2022 and ongoing	ongoing: social media series on pilot members, dedicated pages on the website, member news/update dissemination, event sharing
	T4. Organising learning roundtables on specific topics + capture and disseminate results in the wider community	Innovative Farmers CarbonFarm ÖMKi (AAFC Started in June and ongoing	2 meetings were organised (early October, mid-November): to conceptualise the new learning roundtable session for the 3rd pilot network meeting. New meetings foreseen in April 2023.
	T5. Evaluation of co-creation and co-design experiences in the pilot network	ÖMKi	Draft evaluation questionnaire will be shared with the members to comment on
	T6. Recommendations on how to increase the size/scale of the pilot network (upscaling)	ÖMKi Other members are welcome to support	An online workshop dedicated to this task is foreseen in March 2023 to discuss ideas on how to structure and frame a larger network (thematic groups, LL national roundtable etc.)
Facilitating networking for future research collaboration	T7. Prepare synergies between the strategic research and innovation agenda of the AE Partnership and the needs and aims of the LL/RI network	ÖMKi	AELLRI SRIA was shared, the deadline for comments was early October.
	T8. Set up a small group within the network that monitors and selects relevant calls for proposal development, and (1) circulates these in the pilot network, and (2) facilitates	Biobase ROADMAP ÖMKi LifeWatch	The group was set up, first meeting took place at the end of September 2022. The group is in the process of screening relevant calls based on which a spreadsheet will be shared in February with the members.

	partner matchmaking for collaboration on proposals.		
Awareness raising about the pilot network	T9. Raise awareness about the pilot network on a national level	ÖMKI	Name of the NCPs will be shared with the members and online discussions will be arranged with national NCPs to promote the pilot network, and pilot members to the national decision-makers.

Appendix 9: Results of Learning Roundtable 2 from the 3rd pilot network meeting

Group 1 – Round 1

Co-creation tool used: Speed boat: Clarifying and agreeing on the big idea together practices used in their LLs

Facilitators: Ana Allamand (Soil Association) and Sylvie Fosselle (ILVO)

Scenario: *Setting up an agroforestry project*

Participants: Innovative Farmers, LifeWatch ERIC, PA4ALL

Roles: farmer, researcher, advisor from an NGO

Ideal goals from the perspective of the roles
<p><u>Farmer:</u> Wants to continue farming: cattle, crops and wants extra revenues from nuts. Wants to diminish risks in his/her farm by diversifying products (nuts, carbon credits).</p> <p><u>Researcher:</u> Wants to measure long-term impact data, at least for 10 years or longer. Needs certainty to implement the project for at least 10 years.</p> <p><u>Advisor from NGO:</u> Wants conservation of the trees. Wants data to show evidence to raise awareness about this agroforestry project to the broader public and to policy makers. Wants to understand this system and improve the knowledge and the advice they give.</p>
Not all goals are compatible, so the participants should scale down their ideal goals
The main problem is at the level of the duration of the project. The farmer agrees that the project will need to last 10-12 years. So, he/she will offer a plot of his/her land to be used for the agroforestry project and cattle will be combined with tree rows. There is an agreement of a certain % of the trees that needs to survive.
Possible risks of the project (internal and external)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Timing and communication: the researchers do something on the field without proper communication which might inhibit the farmer of following his seasonal scheme. (internal)

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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The funding stops after the project (external). • Because of drought, the trees die (external). • The researcher/advisor changes job (internal). • The farmer dies and the kids do not want to continue (internal). • The farmer cuts the trees (internal).
Opportunities of the project (internal and external)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By doing research on the farm, the researcher will meet new farmers and this is an opportunity for having more data or more potential areas for in situ research. • The farmer might have access to more academic knowledge. • A network will be built for knowledge and experience exchange.
Next steps
The participants indicated that they would design a project plan and timeline, discussed with the three of them. Then, they would make an official agreement between the three parties.

Group 1 – Round 2

Co-creation tool used: **Speed boat: Clarifying and agreeing on the big idea together practices used in their LLs**

Facilitators: Ana Allamand (Soil Association) and Sylvie Fosselle (ILVO)

Scenario: Implementing a low tillage system with adapted low tillage machinery

Roles: farmer association representative, researcher, technician from machinery designing company

Participants: CarbonFarm, ROADMAP, Biobase

Ideal goals from the perspective of the roles
<p><u>Farmer association:</u> Wants to design a low tillage system and implement it on the fields. Wants sufficient yields. The association wants to scale this system up to other farmers of the association. They would like to have some training material on this as well.</p> <p><u>Researcher:</u> Wants reliable data. Wants established treatments maintained for minimum 2 years to compare effects with no low tillage fields.</p> <p><u>Machinery company:</u> Wants to develop a precision, low tillage machinery which he can scale up. He needs 2 years or rather 2 growing seasons for developing it. In the first year the prototype needs to be developed and in the second year the machine should be market ready. Would like to apply for a patent for the newly developed machinery for low tillage. Wants to sell the products.</p>
Not all goals are compatible, so the participants should scale down their ideal goals
The participants agree quickly that the experiment needs to last 2 years. The goals were compatible.
Possible risks of the project (internal and external)

- The machinery will not be well treated by the farmer.
- There will be no good communication (in advance) between the farmers and machinery company.
- The development of the machine will be too late because data comes too late.
- It will be not clear what to develop and build.
- The prototype will not be usable for certain weed control.
- There can be bad weather that destroys the field and effects the yield negatively. The farming infrastructure might get damaged.
- Lack of uptaking of the low tillage system.
- Lack of funding.
- The biggest financial risk is for the farmer.

Opportunities of the project (internal and external)

- A well-designed low tillage system.
- Lesser effort to farm.
- Better soil health.
- More members for the association.
- Better research methods for co-creation (in LLS).
- More ideas for research from the farmers.
- Potential for the machinery company to sell more products.
- For the farmers, they have tested machines.
- The machinery company has farmers in the future that can help developing machinery (by implementing a prototype system on their farm).

Next steps

- Participants should design a plan with description of the idea for the low tillage system and agree on timing and planning.
- Find farmers to cooperate with.
- Organise a dinner for the farmers and stakeholders.
- Contact the right experts.
- Make contracts and agreements.
- Apply for relevant funding.
- Allocation of resources.

Group 2 – Round 1

Co-creation tool used: [Needs Register: Recording Stakeholders Needs & Assessing Responsiveness](#)

Facilitators: Chris McPhee (AAFC) and May Hobeika (Ecologic)

Scenario: to develop a living lab on the sequestration of carbon in agricultural soils and to reduce emissions of GHGs

Participants: Hessen Practice Network, LLAEBIO, Inofa, Guadalinfo

Roles: farmers, biophysical scientists, social scientists, economists, regional government

Needs of the roles

Economist:

The economist needs an overview of costs and benefits of the farm (data) (i) before and (ii) after the implementation of practices.

Information on how open farmers are to share accountancy data.

The biophysical scientist:

Needs to implement restrictions on the farming system to get rigorous and publishable results.

Needs data on:

- Soil analysis (mechanical, chemical) for existing situation,
- Carbon footprint (using different methods),
- Effort of practice on yields/ profits.

Social scientist:

Needs to survey the intrinsic motivation of each participant before the project starts.

Farmer:

Needs to differentiate from competing farms through low environmental footprint, need to make sure carbon sequestration practices don't spread disease: agronomic study; and results that can be marketed in the short run.

Needs to know what agronomic practices can be implemented in the plot; Need to know how biophysical scientist comes up with methodology to determine which practices can be implemented.

Needs introduction/ training to report data on practices for self-reporting (2 days).

Plans to measure effects on yields and profits.

Regional government:

Wants to create effective schemes from regional government:

- Understand why policymakers are involved
- Evidence on the benefits for society
- Understand how to improve existing schemes

Wants to understand what policymakers could offer farmers to make the region an example on carbon sequestration and reach policy objectives.

Wants to understand the added value of having the taxpayer pay for compensation.

Wants to understand how to build trust, how to reduce bureaucracy of policy schemes and adjust monitoring to foster appreciation.

Questions and reflections on the usability of the tool

- What do you do with conflicting needs in the group process? If you realise in the continuous steps that some needs are outdated, how do you integrate them?
Translate needs in an action plan/ framework and a timeline and discuss with a group, which needs can be fulfilled and how to action to fulfil every actor's needs.
- When is this done? Do we have a start funding or are we a LL that still needs funding?
If so, need to streamline needs to the funding call and decide how to priorities the needs.
- How to harmonise the group process? What possibilities do you have as group to decide what needs to pursue or not? Ex: different timelines between the farmer and the regional government
- Social scientists needs: very important for diffusion of innovation – how do you integrate social scientists needs into activities? Content analysis.

- Value of anticipating the needs register on an ongoing basis? It makes sense for large projects, second step of refreshing is useful to learn from experience (evolution of the needs)
- Is it useful in the start process of such a project that comes into the group? Or should it come in at a later stage?
Value of inviting policymakers to the kick-off meeting: gather the needs of the group without them and then have the actors in the group to add on them in a second step.

Group 2 – Round 2

Co-creation tool used: [Needs Register: Recording Stakeholders Needs & Assessing Responsiveness](#)

Facilitators: Chris McPhee (AAFC) and May Hobeika (Ecologic)

Scenario: to develop a living lab on the sequestration of carbon in agricultural soils and to reduce emissions of GHGs

Participants: Innovative Farmers, LifeWatch ERIC, PA4ALL

Roles: farmers, biophysical scientists, social scientists, economists

Needs of the roles

Economist:

Needs data on farmers' inputs, time use, labor according to different farming practices.

The biophysical scientist:

Needs land/plot for biophysical analysis (carbon exchange) and for trials.

Needs publishable results.

Social scientist:

Needs agreement on commitment for rigorous trials on carbon sequestration: same crops, same treatment.

Needs evaluation of stakeholders on co-creative process and the effects on local community.

Needs assessment of (farmers') understanding of carbon sequestration.

Farmer:

Needs information on methods for carbon sequestration and practices from scientist.

Needs to know how to grow crops with different practices than before.

Needs calculation for traditional vs. low-carbon production (including credits) to compare costs and benefits.

Needs compensation for risk.

Questions and reflections on the usability of the tool

- LifeWatch Eric: example of project with 72 partners – the need register tool may be more relevant than a survey to understand each others' needs and manage expectations
- PA4ALL: example of IPM project – understanding the overview of needs of different farmers to decide what pest to focus on in small groups
- Stakeholders can reevaluate if they still want to participate in the LL and deal with other actors' needs/ might drop out.

- The initial discussion on needs has value, commitment to tool might reveal new needs and go deeper.
- How to address conflicting needs? Refine understanding of the needs

Group 3 – Round 1

Co-creation tool used: 1. Ground Rules: Identification of Opportunities and Challenges of Agreement-based Cooperation

Facilitators: Korinna Varga (ÖMKi) and Valéria Csonka (ÖMKi)

Scenario: Implementing a low tillage system with adapted low tillage machinery

Roles: farmers, researcher, machinery design company

Participants: CarbonFarm, ROADMAP, Biobase

ACT questions discussed:

"In your world...

...how important are punctuality and time limits?

...are there consequences of being late or missing deadlines?

...what is a comfortable physical distance for interacting in the workplace?

...should people volunteer for assignments or wait to be nominated?

...what group behaviours are valued (helping others, not complaining)?"

- For the farmer, punctuality most of the time is important, to always agree on « when » with the rest of the stakeholders and to be informed in advance if something changes. However, due to weather uncertainties and what/when something can be done on the field, farmer can be unpunctual as he/she has to respond quickly to urgent matters in order to mitigate risks or avoid financial failures.
- The researcher and machinery company can be quite flexible and adaptable to time changes as far as they are informed in advance
- RULE 1. Punctuality is important and time limits should be set, but depending on the circumstances flexibility and adaptability to changes might be required. Therefore, everyone should be informed in advance about changes in order to prepare.
- RULE 2. Being late is not very well tolerated by either stakeholders, all of them have to plan field or design works which might result in financial losses or not delivering properly on the project. It is important to have a plan with a timeline (plan a year ahead if possible) and clear roles for the stakeholders.
- Farmer should be compensated if lateness (no fault of his own) results in loss of yield or other financial losses.
- RULE 3. Farmer is willing to work voluntarily until the assignments are fit well into their daily farming practice. However, when extra work is required (e.g. new data capture and recording), he/she should be paid. The researcher should help in the technical side of assignments, in analysis and explanation of the results.
- RULE 4. Helping one another is expected from every stakeholders since they are in this project together. However, complaints should be voiced and not to let them fester.
- RULE 5. It is important to have a system for information sharing : results/concepts, everything that furthers the project should be broadly shared with everyone, but sensitive information (e.g. commercial values, patents) should be kept confidential and restricted for a few who is concerned.

SPEAK questions discussed:

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"In your world...

...is a promise an aspiration or a guarantee?
...which is most important: directness or harmony?
...are irony and sarcasm appreciated?
...do interruptions signal interest or rudeness?
...does silence mean reflection or disengagement?
...should dissenting views be aired in public or discussed off-line?
...is unsolicited feedback welcome?"

- RULE 6. Trust among group members is paramount, therefore promise is a guarantee that should be kept. But in order to achieve trust, clear communication and understanding of everyone's needs/wants/goals/benefits/ risks should be discussed
- RULE 7. Directness is valued, no one should be restricted in one's speech
- RULE 8. Irony is not appreciated by the stakeholders, a neutral tone should be set without any jokes, sarcasm or rudeness. What might be an understandable and funny joke within academia and among researchers, that might not be valued by farmers.
- RULE 9. It is important to respect each other's business (farmers, machinery company), especially the risks that the stakeholders take with the project
- RULE 10. Arrive to a common understanding of the ultimate objective of the project and how it affects stakeholder's profit/yields.

Group 3 – Round 2

Co-creation tool used: 1. Ground Rules: Identification of Opportunities and Challenges of Agreement-based Cooperation

Facilitators: Korinna Varga (ÖMKi) and Valéria Csonka (ÖMKi)

Scenario: Implementing a low tillage system with adapted low tillage machinery

Roles: farmers, researcher, machinery design company

Participants: Hessen Practice Network, LLAEBIO, Inofa, Guadalinfo

THINK questions discussed:

"In your world...

...is uncertainty viewed as a threat or an opportunity?
...what's more important: the big picture or the details?
...is it better to be reliable or flexible?
...what is the attitude toward failure?
...how do people tolerate deviations from the plan?"

- RULE 11. Identify uncertainties for the different stakeholders in the very beginning of the project, agree on what is certain and is not. Make a plan on how to deal with uncertainties.
- RULE 12. Look out for internally created certainties (actors might create) and have an external expert to validate the promises that were made by the actors to one another
- RULE 13. Set out the magnitude of failure, what is at stake for the project, who is taking the risks and set up a compensation system for all stakeholders.
- RULE 14. Deviations are acceptable in the project depending on the scale, the effects and adaptability of actors.

FEEL questions discussed:

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"In your world...

...what emotions (positive and negative) are acceptable and unacceptable to display in a business context?

...how do people express anger or enthusiasm?

...how would you react if you were annoyed with a teammate (with silence, body language, humour, through a third party)?"

- RULE 15. Positive and negative emotions are both acceptable until they are displayed in a respectful manner. Only showing positive emotions and giving positive feedback may backfire on the long run. Seeing negative emotions help to get to know your partner better, his/her underlying motivations which builds trust.
- RULE 16. Expression of anger, enthusiasm or annoyance should be expressed in a moderate, measured way as different personalities react to these feelings in a different way.
- RULE 17. Have a facilitator for the project group (other than the coordinator) who observes partner's behavior and reactions and to whom actors can turn to privately.

Appendix 10: Pilot member specific competencies

Occitanum is working on a tool and different indicators regarding the use of digital technologies. So, they have expertise in modelling and multicriteria and multi-actor assessment and practical experience.

ÖMKI has expertise in on-farm methodologies, networking, documented methods, and the ability to teach (for newcomers) and share them. They also have experience in multi-actor product development, e.g., knowledge about how to develop products with a variety of actors of the food chain (workshop).

PA4ALL has expertise in ecosystem building, understanding of main issues to address, capability to assign right people to be part of the problem solving and a wide network and are integrated in different organisations.

Innovative Farmers has expertise around networking (but no guide) and in forming farmer groups and facilitating conversation. However, they very often use external advisors from the Soil Association who launched the Innovative Farmers programme.

LLAEBIO has experience with systems thinking.

OasYs has expertise in systemic approach for mixed crop-dairy system.

LifeWatch is strong in co-creation of digital tools for data/knowledge management, a community of stakeholders working on agroecology and linking biodiversity with environmental processes.

CropSys has expertise in policy requirements and national framework, collaboration with industrial partners and farm advisors but not so much with other stakeholders and scientific communication.

ZAPVS is well experienced in biodiversity monitoring and biodiversity and ecosystem functioning.

AAFC is working as a network of living labs to share results, data, intellectual property etc. They have experience in modelling/satellite imagery, competencies among biophysical scientists, in surveys/analysis, evaluation of living labs (e.g., research agenda, scoping review, building useful indicators for managing living labs and for convincing funders).

Appendix 11: Role of the Future Network

1. Developing skills for facilitation and organisation of co-creation sessions, both at the design level of co-creation and at the level of basic facilitation of events.

2. Developing skills and knowledge on how to set up a LL/RI:

This knowledge and skills can be developed by offering:

- A platform to share best practices, e.g., showcasing best practices to motivate actors/raise awareness. Participants indicated that mainly consumers and other value chain actors are the targets that they are struggling to connect with. It might be relevant to showcase best practices in case studies that do connect and engage with these kind of actors (exchanging best practices and learning from mistakes)
- Training sessions and workshop
- A library of best practices (taking context into account)
- 1–2-page guides
- Simple videos instead of complicated documents
- Space for organising distributed experiments based on key drivers of change. Individual LL/RI could experiment with these key drivers to test them by doing socio-ecological experiments. Data can be shared by Virtual Lab. Key drivers and challenges might be the themes that can be covered with the thematic working groups within the network.

Participants noted that, in Europe, many different cultural contexts exist, which might also have an impact on engaging farmers and facing the challenges. Even more, in different countries, there is a different organisation of innovation and knowledge systems, so different methodologies or strategies may be needed to bring together different stakeholders. Furthermore, different Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) exists in different countries. So, strategies to bring stakeholders together might also be different between countries/regions. Therefore, guidance with specific practices might be useful that takes these cultural differences into account. The problem that countries have in setting up LL are probably shared, but the way to deal with them or solutions might depend on the context. The network should provide general building blocks for capacity building (participatory, agroecology, social...) which can be specified in local contexts because education and training are culturally defined, languages are different and farmers and some actors of the agri-food value chain (advisors...) do not always understand English. However, participants mentioned that the national level will remain crucial to organise capacity building, even when a European network is created, but in some countries, they do not want to spend funds on organising capacity building.

Other benefits of a European network might be:

- Information exchange at the European level,
- Development of a suitable funding strategy,
- Increasing robustness of evidence and potential for awareness raising of opportunities and benefits of transitions for farmers, consumers, and other actors in the value chain,
- Increasing impact and outreach – Potential for a European network to become a key driver of change,
- Organisation of events.

Appendix 12: Feedback on the experiences

Feedback on the 1st pilot network meeting

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General feedback on the online format and MURAL:

- The tasks were more straightforward and easier to follow for those who are more computer-savvy and used to online workshops, but others with lack of experience couldn't contribute as much. Makes the work more convenient and quicker to work with predefined information (agroecology interests, needs and expectations) which mainly requires approval/disapproval and less thinking from the members. Face-to-face contacts were missing, which would have helped more detailed and deeper understanding of members' thoughts and (mis)understandings and necessary intervention of facilitators.
- Although the work and interactions in small groups were very useful, members signalled that they would have talked more during a physical meeting, compared to the online format.
- Music was played during WP5 workshop which did not help the thinking of the members, however for a few it was soothing.
- Useful visual representation of results, inputs gathered before on MURAL which helped the members' understanding on expectations and needs of the pilot network. Although the work and interactions in small groups in the WP6 workshop were very useful, discussion only occurred in one of the groups. In the other group, members filled in the Mural quietly and discussion was not initiated by the facilitator which created a strange, impersonal environment.

Joint activities

- The three methods applied were interesting, useful, interactive, and served the purpose of the workshop, though the timeframe was too short and would have been way more productive physically.
- Many members saw collaboration potential right away during match-making due to the number of different types of information visually provided on each initiative (not just hearing it in the presentations) which got them curious.
- The challenges part was difficult to fill in for some (less time and complex answers were required).
- A few signalled that it was difficult to understand what other initiatives are aiming to do and how we will work further by collaborating with one another as it was new and hard to comprehend and process this much information presented at once.
- The follow-up of this exercise would be important, especially in case of project and non-project partners teaming up to bridge the gaps.

Capacity building and competencies

- The overall workshop was well-structured but some felt it was a bit abstract compared to other workshops in the pilot meeting.
- Tasks were a bit difficult to do, felt vaguer and different, members often got lost and confused, not really getting the point on the different level of experiences.
- The tasks were not self-explanatory.
- The rowing example before the exercise that explained the objective of the workshop in advance was really creative and was a good warm-up.

Building the Virtual Lab

- The workshop was concrete, well-built, with visual tools used that served well the mapping tasks.
- There was a perceptible difference between LLs and RIs in understanding the importance of the Virtual Lab and the related tasks. Mainly RIs expressed that they are very much interested in Virtual Lab and could use it in the future, but still need some work or further workshops to better understand it.

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- However, for some, mainly LLs, the exercise and used method was not entirely understandable and they could not make the relation with their LL activities.

Feedback on the 2nd pilot network meeting

- Very well organised day and a half packed with participatory exercises and lively discussions, participants did not get bored at all.
- The synergetic interactions among participants were improved in this hybrid meeting, in comparison with previous online meetings.
- Despite being hybrid event, the infrastructure and technical environment was taken care of, online participation was ensured. However, the interaction via online was way more difficult when there was a good dynamic in the room.
- The field visit was the highlight of the workshop, and these visits need to be repeated at each pilot meeting.
- Energiser activity was fun and required a great amount of thinking and exchange with all participants. It was unfortunate that the ones who joined online could not partake in the energiser.
- The feedback calls are extremely useful for giving well-thought out evaluation about the meeting, so the follow-up is taken care of.
- It would have been better if there is a dedicated session just about the ALL-Ready project and the objectives of different WPs. There were some new representatives who did not participate on the 1st meeting, therefore they didn't know well the status of the project.
- The lack of time to discuss during the different session was a major issue both for members and for WP facilitators.

Feedback on the 3rd pilot network meeting:

- Very well and tightly organised two and a half days packed with participatory exercises, field trip and lively discussions.
- It was incredibly important to meet again in-person, especially to meet with new members and with those who couldn't attend at previous meetings.
- The overview about the project WPs and its achievements was quite informative and useful for the majority, but some noted that it was unnecessary.
- Despite being hybrid event, the infrastructure and technical environment was taken care of, online participation was ensured. There was no major problem with the connection and sound for online participants.
- Despite the bad weather, the field visit was extremely valuable and completely different than the Demo Day in Ghent which shows the diversity that the members bring into the network.
- The feedback calls are useful for giving well-thought out evaluation about the meeting, so the follow-up is taken care of.
- The tools learned/trained during the Learning roundtable session were generally useful. Many signaled that they will try them out in their LL/RI network and will report back on their usability. However for some, the tools were very basic or already known.
- It was also good that there was sufficient time to discuss with the members during the different sessions.
- Some complained about the length and the intensity of the programme and suggested to make it shorter next time.

Feedback on 4th pilot network meeting

No major remarks were mentioned by the members in relation to the interactive sessions besides mentioning the structured, well-thought-out organisation and the need to have more group exercises and less presentation next time. But some specific remarks are worth mentioning in relation to the trainings.

a) Living lab model, real-life experimentation & facilitation techniques training:

- Participants reflected on the possibility to apply the facilitation techniques with the users of their LL/RI. Some of them shared the experience of having already implemented some of the techniques and similar ones with great success. The content and material were appreciated by the participants, and it was perceived as a very dynamic training, based on real-life cases with its challenges and opportunities.
- Participants were interested in learning about the selection of new facilitation techniques dedicated to LL and getting to know the concrete examples.
- Members highlighted that this training was not really focused on agroecology LLs, but rather on urban and tech LLs, so it would have been nice to adapt the presentations to real agriculture examples. The exercises done were also less effective due to the disconnect with agricultural LL realities.

b) System thinking training:

- The energiser as introduction to systems thinking was appreciated by the participants.
- The general introduction on systems thinking included many examples on agroecology and agriculture to make the direct link with the field of interest of the participants in the room.
- A (short) implementation of the causal loop diagram was applied to a specific case (water shortage) introduced by one of the participants.
- General satisfaction was expressed by participants in the topics of the training:
- Introduction to systems thinking (36,7 % extremely useful, 27,3% very useful, 27,3 moderately useful).
- Actor mapping exercise (18,2 % extremely useful, 18,2 % very useful, 45,5% moderately useful) .
- Causal loop diagram exercise (18,2 % extremely useful, 36,4 % very useful, 27,3% moderately useful).
- The open discussion was appreciated by the participants as it was perceived as useful moment to share perspectives and views with others. The two tools presented can be used in the LL.